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Abstract	<p>This document is the Deliverable D6.2 for the AD4GD project. It presents the final results achieved in the context of Tasks T6.1, T6.2, T6.3, and T6.4. The document is a follow-up version of the Deliverable 6.1 "Pilot Technical Implementation Planning, Implementation and Assessment" that reported on pilot establishment, design of workflow and requirements analysis.</p> <p>The purpose of Deliverable D6.2 is to review and report on the integration of accessible, re-usable tools and workflows, including re-use and extension of existing tools, semantics and standards as well as bespoke development of 12 new interoperable components and approaches within the project. Where component reports have already been published within other deliverables that document underpinning technologies and services, these will be signposted to avoid redundancy and duplication.</p> <p>This collection of Green Deal Data Space components is presented in the form of tested FAIR workflows that consume, use and produce data and metadata for the three identified pilot case studies, to facilitate data-driven decision making on Green Deal priority topics.</p>
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	<p>The progress described includes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • re-use and extension of existing re-usable components, data and services which can support the pilots and, more broadly, the Green Deal Data Space; • identification of remaining gaps, and of components required to fill those gaps; • development and integration of the identified components; • evaluation of workflow and interface performance, and of output quality and consistency. <p>Our human-centred co-design approach has enabled us to work closely with sister projects and existing GEO initiatives to ensure efficiency and interoperability.</p> <p>For each pilot, the reader may refer to D6.1 for in-depth descriptions of the initial rationale, indicators and stakeholders, and evaluation of the relative contribution of EO, citizen science, socio-economic and IoT data. In D6.2 we show how the workflows developed to support some areas of the Green Deal decision-making have been developed, and illustrate how a range of data and services can be transparently and reproducibly integrated within the Green Deal Data Space to generate scientifically defensible outputs which can be easily discovered, re-used and visualised by stakeholders. The corresponding assessment of scalability, performance, and technology convergence can be found in D6.3.</p> <p>Throughout the report, URLs are given for supporting open-source demonstrations, instances, or code repositories. The overall project repository of technical resources can be found on GitHub (https://github.com/AD4GD).</p> <p>In the course of the project, the collaborative development and iterative integration was supported by four face-to-face project hackathons in October 2023, February 2024, September 2024, and April 2025.</p>
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Disclaimer	<p>Views and opinions expressed in this deliverable are those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union the United Kingdom or Switzerland. Neither the European Union nor United Kingdom nor Switzerland can be held responsible for them</p>

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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIM	Agriculture Information Model
API	Application Programming Interface
AQ	Air Quality
ARIMA	AutoRegressive Integrated Moving Average
AWS	Amazon Web Services
B3	B Cubed (sister project)
CAMS	Copernicus Atmosphere Monitoring Service
CDSE	COPERNICUS Data Space Ecosystem
cGAN	Conditional Generative Adversarial Network
cGANs	Conditional Generative Adversarial Networks
CitSci	Citizen Science (also known as community science, participatory science..)
CSV	Comma-Separated Values
CSV-W	CSV for the Web
CSW	Catalogue Service for the Web
DAPS	Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service
DAT	Dynamic Attribute Tokens
DBF	dBase Database File
DOPA	Digital Observatory for Protected Areas
EAV	Essential Agriculture Variables
EBV	Essential Biodiversity Variables
ECV	Essential Climate Variables
EDC	Eclipse Dataspace Connector ¹
EO	Earth Observation
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
FCN	Fully Convolutional Networks
FLC	Functional Landscape Connectivity
FROST	FRaunhofer Opensource SensorThings-Server
FTP	File Transfer Protocol
GBDV	Global Biodiversity Data Viewer

¹ Sometimes also referred to Eclipse Dataspace Component.

GBIF	Global Biodiversity Information Facility
GD	Green Deal
GDDS	Green Deal Data Space
GDIM	Green Deal Information Model
GEO	Group on Earth Observation
GeoTIFF	Tagged Image File Format (georeferenced)
GPU	Graphical Processing Unit
GUF	Geospatial User Feedback
GUI	Graphical User Interface
HTTP	Hipertext Transfer Protocol
IAM	Access Management
ICT	Index of Terrestrial Connectivity
IDSA	International Data Space Association
IoT	Internet of Things
IT	information Technology
IUCN	International Union for Conservation of Nature
JPEG	Joint Photographic Experts Group
JRC	Joint Research Centre (European Commission)
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
JSON-LD	JSON Linked Data
KER	Key Exploitable Result
LESRPE	Listado de Especies Silvestres en Régimen de Protección Especial (Spanish List of Wild Species under Special Protection)
LSTM	Long Short-Term Memory
LULC	Land-Use / Land-Cover
LZW	Lempel-Ziv-Welch (compression algorithm)
ML	Machine Learning
MNB	Mean Normalized Bias
MQTT	Message Queuing Telemetry Transport
MSA	MiraMon Support App
MSE	Mean Squared Error
MVD	Minimum Viable Dataspace
NDTrI	Normalized Difference Trophic Index
ODC	Open Data Cube
OGC	Open Geospatial Consortium
OpenEO	Open source Earth Observation

OSM	OpenStreetMap
OWL	Web Ontology Language
pH	Potential of Hydrogen
PM	Particulate Matter
RDF	Resource Description Framework
REST	Representational State Transfer
RMSE	Root Mean Square Error
SARIMA	Seasonal Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average
SCL	Scene Classification Band
SHACL	Shapes Constraint Language
SOSA	Sensors, Observations Samples and Actuators
STA	SensorThings API
STApplus	SensorThings API plus
TAPIS	Tables from APIs
TIFF	Tagged Image File Format
Turtle	Terse RDF Triple Language
UI	User Interface
UR	User Requirements
VGI	Volunteered Geographical Information
WAI	Water Availability Index
ZSTD	Zstandard (compression algorithm)

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document is the Deliverable D6.2 for the AD4GD project. It presents the final results achieved in the context of Tasks T6.1, T6.2, T6.3, and T6.4. The document is a follow-up version of the Deliverable D6.1 "Pilot Technical Implementation Planning, Implementation and Assessment"² that reported on pilot establishment, design of workflow and requirements analysis.

In the AD4GD project we present re-usable elements of the Green Deal Data Space (GDDS) to address the challenges of three pilots focussing on water pollution, biodiversity and air quality. We have successfully integrated new data types to each pilot (e.g. EO, CitSci, socio-economic or IoT) to improve analysis and workflows that generate results ready for decision-making. The project has delivered a range of solutions which are appropriate to stakeholders at different technical expertise levels and with different constraints and priorities. For example, a non-expert user may engage with the processing chain of the water pilot to query the state and predicted water availability for a lake, through a simple interactive interface (called Splashboard). At the other end of the technical scale, a user with a modicum of IT experience can replicate our habitat connectivity computations, including powerful enrichment of landcover maps with data from citizen scientists and authoritative databases, or can set up their own platform for ingestion and semantic enrichment of sensor data, by deploying platform-agnostic and modular tools that have been published in the project's open-source GitHub repository. This range of outcomes has been designed for re-use and extension as the GDDS evolves in the future.

To implement the three pilots, we identified a total of twelve technical components (including software tools, protocols and approaches) as a materialisation of necessary Dataspace building blocks, and these are deployed as part of the AD4GD Dataspace. The collaborative development and iterative integration of these open-source components was supported by four face-to-face project hackathons in October 2023, February 2024, September 2024, and April 2025. The components are described in Sections 2.1 to 2.12, and their usage and integration in the pilots is explained in Section 3. Throughout the report, URLs are given for supporting open-source demonstrations, instances or code repositories, and the overall project repository of technical resources can be found on GitHub (<https://github.com/AD4GD>).

A number of these components are used across the domains and themes of the pilots, successfully demonstrating the interoperability which will be required for tackling interdisciplinary challenges in the European Green Deal. For example, the work throughout has connected to a single semantic interoperability framework – the Green Deal Information Model (GDIM), defined in WPI, and publicly hosted on the OGC's RAINBOW server. Vocabularies relevant to the project were defined and cross-linked to equivalent terms using an RDF model defined by partners PSNC and OGC. This allows us to publish near-real-time data streams as STA / STApplus services for use both within the project and beyond in the wider GDDS. Metadata for our data inputs and outputs is semantically enhanced with terms from the GDIM as keywords and conceptual descriptions wherever possible. In addition to the final outputs of the pilots, much of the intermediate value-added data is available via STA or STApplus datastreams³, which are also accessible through Eclipse Dataspace Connector (EDC) which permits negotiated contracts. The EDC solution is relevant to almost all stages of the AD4GD workflows – wherever access to commercial or sensitive data requires a trusted negotiation or contract, and in the second half of the project the progress on developing and integrating this solution has strengthened the opportunities for engagement of commercial players in the GDDS.

Pilot 1

Pilot 1 (Water) was led by KWB and related to urban lakes in Berlin, where we specifically focussed on water availability and quality, which particularly affect provisioning and recreation ecosystem services. In

² <https://zenodo.org/records/10839023>

³ e.g. [https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/MultiDatastreams\(23\)/Sensor](https://frost.iotlab.com/sensorthings/v1.1/MultiDatastreams(23)/Sensor)

this pilot, satellite data and volunteered CitSci measurements were used to enrich a Dataspace which is currently dominated by IoT sources such as *in-situ* sensors for water level, conductivity, oxygen etc. The available *in-situ* data was sparse, especially for water quality in smaller lakes and so these additional data sources allowed the AD4GD to build prediction models based on machine learning and on classification models leveraging remote sensing. This allows stakeholders to monitor, predict and visualise the state and trend of water availability and quality via the 'Splashboard' UI. A Water Quality Index representing trophic state (NDTrI) and a Water Availability Index (WAI) were developed and validated as part of this pilot, in partnership between KWB, AU and ATOS.

Several sources of data for the pilot were accessible early in the project through open and standardised APIs, including some lake and groundwater level data published via the Berlin Senate's 'Wasserportal' and a range of environmental, cadastral and administrative boundaries available through the Senate's 'FIS-Broker' platform. The pilot succeeded in semantically enriching and harmonising this data and integrating a range of underused data sources such as EO Sentinel-2 data and CitSci observations. For example, to monitor measures relevant for recreation and water quality estimation, KWB engaged with the developers of the CrowdWater monitoring app to produce a version appropriate for lakes, and this was deployed with a set of volunteers during the second half of the project.

In-situ sensor data is not commonly available for these small lakes, and this is particularly important for benchmarking EO data and for calibrating its analysis, since 'ground truth' from smaller lakes in Berlin is so sparse in space and time. Solutions were piloted and calibrated at a subset of lakes, including IoT oxygen sensors installed in partnership with the Berlin district authorities and *in-situ* measurements of temperature, nutrients and pH collected in partnership with local schools, using low-cost devices. This contributed to the Data Trustworthiness Framework defined in WP4.

The 'Wasserportal' data was semantically uplifted using terms from the Green Deal Information Model (GDIM - hosted on the OGC's RAINBOW server) to generate several live STA datastreams. The metadata published on Geonetwork (and in the EDC federated catalogue) for these datastreams includes terms from the GDIM to enhance the meaning of the discovered data. New data are semantically enriched as they become available, following the methods developed in WP1 and WP3, and ingested by ATOS to build and validate prediction models for a water availability index (WAI).

In parallel, water quality trends are evaluated using the NDTrI trophic index developed and calibrated within the project and computed using Sentinel-2 data from the Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem (CDSE). Because this computation workflow uses OpenEO, it can be deployed locally or on the CSDE in a platform-agnostic. Both water quality and availability data are provided to users through the interactive 'Splashboard' UI, which was defined and developed via 2 iterations of working prototypes, and tested by end-users. This demonstrates the flexibility of underlying workflows and computations, and the fact that a distributed set of data and services can be federated and provided to the user in a seamless way by exploiting the available open standards.

In addition to the publication of outputs via the Splashboard, the value-added harmonised data is also available via STA datastreams and optionally through EDC contracts.

Pilot 2

Pilot 2: (Biodiversity) was led by AU and CREA in partnership. It identified key locations for landscape functional connectivity and endangered species persistence by explicitly combining and cross-validating the results from different accepted modelling approaches, based on time series of land-use / land-cover (LULC) maps. Strong collaboration with B3, one of the sister projects participating in the GDDS call, allowed the connectivity results to be verified in a replicable way, through ingestion of species occurrence cubes based on observations from the Global Biodiversity Information Facility (GBIF). The project also benefitted from collaboration with JRC's Knowledge Centre for Biodiversity, whose open-standards approach meant

that we were able to seamlessly integrate one of the DOPA / GBDV APIs for species distribution data into the verification workflow

Satellite and satellite-derived data and species observations from CitSci are established tools for mapping and monitoring species distributions and landscapes. IoT technologies can also contribute to monitor threats and verify their impacts on endangered species, and volunteered geographical information (VGI) on features such as roads and rivers can significantly improve the representation of landscape permeability. Therefore, these two data sources (IoT and VGI) were integrated in the form of camera trap data and OpenStreetMap features. The resulting pre-processing and computational methods for connectivity calculation can be complex to replicate and thus, in addition to a user client for accessing the workflow, this pilot developed open-source modular analysis components (Data4Land) which can be deployed on a range of platforms. (Kriukov et al, 2025). Initial testing was performed on European Weather Cloud VMs provided by ECMWF, scaleup and optimisation of connectivity computations through dockerised applications were successfully deployed and tested on two different HPC clusters (at PSNC and AU) during the second half of the project. Functional Landscape Connectivity (FLC) computations were experimentally performed in other ways - consuming less resource and taking less time - through emulation of the process based on a deep learning approach which takes the LULC map as input and the computed FLC map as a target. The metadata published on the AD4GD Geonetwork catalogue⁴ for these outputs incorporate some provenance information regarding the machine learning processing steps, as well as quality reports on the structural similarity and MSE of the results. In this way we fully exploit the rich ISO 19115 metadata model to fully document project outcomes and assist a user in evaluating their fitness-for-purpose.

To provide automatic linking and cross-walking of outputs with other biodiversity resources, the ISO metadata for connectivity outputs has been enriched with relevant terms representing Essential Biodiversity Variables Products, which were incorporated into the GDIM. The metadata also incorporate some provenance information regarding processing steps such as machine learning and Data4Land enrichment, and include terms from the GDIM for semantic context. In addition to the publication of outputs via the BioConnect GUI, the original LULC series is also available from OGC API coverages reading from open data cube interfaces, and optionally through EDC connectors.

To increase the plausibility of outputs and ensure the practical and scientific implementation of connectivity computation workflows, it is necessary to build dialog with relevant stakeholders, identify specific species and sites of interest, any new sources of relevant data, and update user stories from various stakeholders, including consultants, governmental and CitSci projects. In the second half of the project, such a specific exercise was carried out for the *Testudo hermannii* species in Albera Natural Park, with the assistance and insight of local experts. In the course of this work, another species presence/absence data from one of the GDDS sister projects was used for validation, in the form of the B3 occurrence cubes for priority species for Catalonia region, produced by GBIF as an experimental data cube format designed to ease specific spatio-temporal and thematic queries. The results are briefly documented in this deliverable and a full investigation has been submitted as a journal manuscript.

In-situ sensor data from camera traps can be useful to verify presence and migration routes on concrete sites by key species of interest, but still requires edge processing to optimise access and increase performance of data access. Edge processing of camera trap data from the Cos4Cloud project and publication of STAplus datastreams on FROST server have been successfully carried out as experimental steps in Pilot 2. The data have not currently captured the study species of interest but the principle of efficient data capture and transparent integration was demonstrated.

⁴ e.g. <https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/ad4gd/eng/catalog.search#/metadata/5964f34b-90d8-400a-bbc3-d1ca36e7d8a2>

To support the visual representation of data used and computed through different stages in Pilot 2, the Bioconnect GUI client and its service interface were further defined and developed via iterations of working prototypes, and tested by end users. GBIF data have also been incorporated into Pilot 2 as an additional means of contextual visualisation for the Bioconnect GUI, through the OGC WMS API.

Pilot 3

Pilot 3 (Air quality and pollution) is a context where the use of Earth Observation (EO) data was already well-established by the pilot leads (ECMWF) through their generation of the authoritative CAMS air quality maps and forecasts, and an important part of this case study was the evaluation of the potential of IoT data and CitSci observations to enrich these products. This has potential to enable further insights into air pollution on a city scale, which is particularly relevant in the context of longitudinal health monitoring and early warning systems. However, these new observations from low-cost sensors must be integrated and systematically quality-checked in order to identify bias and error, and to ensure a scientifically robust result. Within Pilot 3, we have evaluated the consistency and trustworthiness of a range of IoT and CitSci observations, with a view that in the future it may be beneficial to incorporate information from these IoT sources into the CAMS forecast model to increase its granularity.

As part of the initial investigations, ECMWF and AU developed approaches to ingest and aggregate data from a range of low-cost sensor sources – initially Plume Flows, Earthsense Zephyrs and Sensor.Community kits, and then additionally PurpleAir and AirGradient instruments. The ingestion approaches have been designed for easy re-use and combination with existing data pipelines as appropriate to support ingestion of AQ data from citizen initiatives and IoT networks that currently publish their data via non-standard APIs. Within the first months of the project, we ingested data from multiple sensor types (including mobile devices) and these data exemplars were used at the project hackathons in Birmingham (October 23) and Torino (February 24) to kickstart experiments on integration and semantic enrichment. Examples of raw data extracted from various sensors reinforced the necessity for semantic mapping: the "Observed Properties" values and the "Units of Measure" are provided in many different ways and this motivated an extension of the ingestion system to ease user-defined semantic annotation and uplift, enabling the export of meaningful metadata compliant with the GDIM alongside the harmonised datastreams.

During the second half of the project, ECMWF developed a rigorous approach based on machine learning for evaluating the practical usability of CitSci / IoT air quality observations (focussing on data from the Sensor.Community network) which has been applied to different regions in Europe that represent different air quality regimes and unique regional characteristics such as orography, air pollution sources and weather patterns. This activity has been a key source of insights and examples for the project's Data Trustworthiness Framework. In this ECMWF's approach is complemented by the collocation functionalities of the AU data ingestion system, which allows the comparison of multiple sensor types within the same spatial bounding box, in order to assess consistency within and between sensor types. The open-source tools developed for data harmonisation and comparison can enrich the practice of citizen scientists by generating assessments of instrument and measurement quality for open analysis and discussion.

1 INTRODUCTION

In the AD4GD project we have practically built and integrated re-useable elements of the GDDS to address data ready for decision-making and monitoring challenges for water pollution, biodiversity and air quality. The European Green Deal challenges are articulated in the project's three pilots, and for each we have striven to improve scientific outputs by integrating forms and sources of data (whether this be EO, CitSci, socio-economic or IoT) which were not originally used to their maximum potential.

During the first half of the project, we developed the initial rationale and identified indicators to be computed and stakeholders for co-design and evaluation of our workflows and end-user tools. During the second half of the project, we have continued with development and integration of bespoke tools and components to complement existing solutions and to deliver open-source workflows which can be transparently replicated, tested and re-used in ongoing GDDS developments. For a detailed discussion of the pilots' context, stakeholders, data priorities and challenges, refer to D6.1. This deliverable will build on the progress and work presented there, as follows:

Section 1.1 situates the pilots in the context of the GDDS and updates the mappings of pilot elements to GDSS building blocks, with a brief explanation of the final workflow(s) that have been developed for each pilot.

Section 2 introduces the technical underpinnings of the pilot workflows. To implement the three pilots, we initially identified a total of twelve technical components (including software tools, protocols and approaches) as a materialisation of necessary building blocks, and these are deployed as part of the AD4GD Dataspace. The following list enumerates the components, specifying the main WP in which each was developed and the pilot(s) in which it is used. The components are described in Sections 2.1 to 2.12.

1. Automated Ingestion of Data from Diverse Low-cost Sensors. Developed in WP6 and identified as a KER. Used in Pilot 3.
2. Evaluation of Connector Solutions. Developed in WP5. Used in Pilot 2
3. Semantic uplift: SPARQL/JSON-LD For Data Exchange: Developed in WP1 and identified as a KER. Used in Pilot 1, 2 and 3
4. Mobilising Data to STApplus with TAPIS. Developed in WP2 and identified as a KER. Used in Pilot 1 and 2
5. Mobilising sensor data with STA and IoT. Developed in WP3 and identified as a KER. Used in Pilot 1 and 2
6. Data Cubes for Consuming, Publishing and Processing Multidimensional Data. Developed in WP4 and identified as KER. Used in Pilot 2
7. Open workflows for habitat connectivity computation. Developed in WP6 and identified as KER. Used in Pilot 2
8. Water modelling and prediction. Developed in WP5 and identified as KER. Used in Pilot 1
9. Data catalogue and metadata. Developed in WP2. Used in Pilot 1, 2 and 3
10. Data catalogue and metadata with Semantic Uplift. Developed in WP1 and identified as KER. Used in Pilot 1, 2 and 3
11. Data Trustworthiness Framework. Developed in WP4. Used in Pilot 3
12. GDDS Semantic Terms - RAINBOW Server. Developed in WP1 and identified as KER. Used in Pilot 1, 2 and 3.

Section 3 explains how each pilot evolved in the second half of the project. This work has required us to work closely with sister projects such as B3 and FAIRiCUBE and with existing GEO initiatives to ensure

efficiency and interoperability. Examples are given of how the project has re-used outputs from other EU projects and research infrastructures, including the APIs from the COPERNICUS Data Space Ecosystem, JRC's Global Biodiversity Data Viewer⁵ and species occurrence cubes from the B3 project⁶. For each pilot, an evaluation section is presented which benchmarks the performance of the delivered solutions against requirements and highlights potential for future extension and re-use.

After the conclusion a list of references, followed by an Annex is presented, giving more detail on pilot 1 research and technical investigations which are not fully described in other deliverables.

1.1 GDDS CONTEXT OF THE PILOTS

The pilot studies cover key challenges relating to European Green Deal priorities, and each requires the transparent and principled use of data and services from multiple sources to support and defend evidence based strategic decision-making. At least some participants in the GDDS will supply commercial or sensitive data, and this has necessitated attention to privacy and contract negotiation within the AD4GD project (e.g. Section 2.2) to complement the open standards and approaches which are exploited and documented elsewhere in this and other deliverables. To set the technical context of the GDDS, we have generated a proposed mapping of Data Spaces Support Centre (DSSC) building blocks to current standards (Noardo et al., 2024). Instead of classifying the building blocks by interoperability, trust and data value, the classification is based on FAIR assets, data models, tools and services. The resulting diagram (Figure 1) goes beyond the Dataspace concept to recognize other processes that augment and feed into the Dataspace, or make use of the assets in the Dataspace. The colouring of this diagram is used to add context to the pilot diagrams which follow.

⁵ <https://dopa.jrc.ec.europa.eu/gbdv/query-builder/>

⁶ <https://docs.b-cubed.eu/guides/occurrence-cube/>

AD4GD

Figure 1: Schematic of elements required to support the delivery of the Green Deal Data Space (adapted from deliverable 3.2 of USAGE project- Grant Agreement no 101059950 and published in Noardo et al., 2024).

The figures below show each pilot study as it can be framed with reference to these building blocks. Successful delivery of the pilots relies on a range of underpinning standards, tools and technical protocols, which are identified in Figure 2, Figure 3, and Figure 4. A number of components are shared between the pilots, and all have been developed or extended in a FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) and modular fashion, enabling re-use beyond the AD4GD project for a sustainable GDDS.

These reference diagrams are comprehensive, and broken down into more specific detail in the following sections. Technical developments which fill identified gaps are described in Section 2, and the final status of each pilot pipeline is reviewed and illustrated in Section 3.

Figure 2: Water pilot.

Pilot 1 (Water) was led by KWB, and related to urban lakes in Berlin – we specifically focussed on water availability and quality, which particularly affect provisioning and recreation ecosystem services. In this pilot, satellite data and volunteered CitSci measurements were used to enrich a Dataspace which is currently dominated by IoT sources such as *in-situ* sensors for water level, conductivity, oxygen etc. The available *in-situ* data was sparse, especially for water quality in smaller lakes and so these additional data sources allowed us to build prediction models based on machine learning and classification models leveraging remote sensing, allowing stakeholders to monitor, predict and visualise the state and trend of water availability and quality via the ‘Splashboard’ UI. A Water Quality Index representing trophic state (NDTrI) and a Water Availability Index (WAI) were developed and validated as part of this pilot, in partnership between KWB, AU and ATOS. The two indices are computed in different workflows (and currently deployed on different platforms) but the pipelines are fully interoperable and thus they can be combined for provision to users through the interactive ‘Splashboard’ UI. The diagram above also shows an example of the use of Eclipse Dataspace Connectors (Section 2.2) to give negotiated access to harmonised and value-added data on lake water levels, which can be discovered, explored and visualised using tools such as the TAPIS component (Section 2.4). The EDC connector solution is actually relevant to many stages of the AD4GD workflows – wherever access to commercial or sensitive data requires a trusted negotiation or contract – but we have restricted their representation on the diagrams to this single example for simplicity’s sake.

Pilot 2: Biodiversity

AD4GD

Figure 3: Biodiversity pilot.

Pilot 2: (Biodiversity) was led by AU and CREAf in partnership. It identified key locations for landscape functional connectivity and endangered species persistence by explicitly combining and cross-validating the results from different accepted modelling approaches, based on time series of land-use / land-cover (LULC) maps. Strong collaboration with the B3 project (one of the Green Deal Data Space sister projects) allowed the connectivity results to be verified in a replicable way, by ingesting species occurrence cubes based on observations from GBIF.

Satellite and satellite-derived data and species observations from CitSci are established tools for mapping and monitoring species distributions and landscapes, IoT technologies can also contribute to monitor threats and verify their impacts on endangered species, and volunteered mappings of geographical features such as roads and rivers can significantly improve the representation of landscape permeability. Therefore, these two data sources were integrated in the form of camera trap data and OpenStreetMap features. The resulting pre-processing and computational methods for connectivity calculation can be complex to replicate and thus, in addition to a user client for accessing the workflow, this pilot developed open-source modular analysis components which can be deployed on a range of platforms (Kriukov et al., 2025). This workflow was demonstrated at a national scale (Catalonia) and at a more localised scale (Albera Natural Park).

Figure 4: Air pilot.

Pilot 3 (Air quality and pollution) is a context where the use of Earth Observation (EO) data was already well-established by the pilot leads (ECMWF) through their generation of the authoritative CAMS air quality maps and forecasts at a global scale (e.g. 10 - 40 km resolution). An important part of this case study was the evaluation of the potential of IoT data and CitSci observations to enrich these products and enable further insights into air pollution on a city scale. This is particularly relevant in the context of health monitoring in the short-term (e.g. early warning systems) as well as long-term (e.g. an improved data base for medical studies). However, these new observations from low-cost sensors must be integrated and systematically quality-checked in order to identify bias and error, and to ensure a scientifically robust result. The pilot made scientific assessments of the feasibility of IoT data integration, using machine learning approaches to evaluate consistency of particulate data from the Sensor.Community network with CAMS (Section 3.3.1). In addition, the ingestion tool for low-cost sensor data (Section 2.1) was significantly extended during the second half of the project to support access to data from a range of user-defined sensors, semantic enrichment of that data using the CSV-W standard, and API services⁷ which allow the exploration and analysis of data from multiple collocated sensor types (Section.3.3.2). Both of these approaches are guided by the Data Trustworthiness framework documented in Section 2.11 and Deliverable 4.3, and can enrich the practice of citizen scientists by contributing assessments of instrument and measurement quality for open analysis and discussion.

⁷ <https://xds-dev.ecmwf.int/datasets/derived-air-quality>

2 TECHNICAL COMPONENTS – IMPLEMENTATION

Figure 5: AD4GD technical components overview (orange: developed by AD4GD; blue: off the shelf).

Different components of the AD4GD Dataspace are combined in Figure 5 to represent the architecture of the project. On the left hand side the types of data source can be seen, as well as the processes by which they are ingested and harmonized using the STApplus data model or the data cube model. In the center the MinIO data repository and the GeoNetwork metadata catalogue represent our internal representation of the data. Semantic enrichment and ML processing create new data that is also stored in MinIO. On the right hand side the EDC is presented as a way to expose AD4GD data in the GDDS (open data can additionally be exposed using standard APIs). External providers can also participate in the GDDS using other types of connectors, and the data in the GDDS can be consumed by visualization tools such as TAPIS and the Graphical UIs specific to Pilot 1 and 2. Some components are already available (such as the EDC) off the shelf but other needed to be developed or personalized.

Components that have been developed in AD4GD are exposed and listed in the project repository on GitHub as shown in Figure 6. Off-the-shelf components, such as MinIO, are not described in GitHub with the exception of EDC, STApplus and GeoNetwork (because best practices developed in the project are documented and stored in GitHub). The following subsections will describe each component.

All Data 4 Green Deal

AD4GD's mission is to co-create and shape the European Green Deal Data Space as an open hub for FAIR data and standards-based services.

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Discussions

Set up discussions to engage with your community!

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People

Invite someone

Top languages

- Jupyter Notebook
- Python
- Java
- TypeScript
- Vue

Most used topics

- habitat-connectivity
- landscape-connectivity
- landscape-ecology
- landscape-metrics
- openstreetmap

Component	Description
Pilot 1: Water Quality	Scenario analysis tools for small Berlin lakes
• RAINBOW Data	Water quality vocabularies published in the OGC RAINBOW hosted instance
• Sentinel-2 Trophic State Estimation	Computing Remote Sensing Indices using OpenEO
• SplashBoard	Tool for displaying indicators of water quality of small urban lakes
Pilot 2: Biodiversity	Determining whether animal habitats are being disconnected
• RAINBOW Data	Essential Biodiversity Variables (EBVs) published in the OGC RAINBOW hosted instance
• Data4Land	Enriching land-use/land-cover data with OSM and protected areas
• Graphab PostProc	Containerised Graphab software for postprocessing
• Miramon Proc	Instructions to run MiraMon ICT for connectivity calculation
• GBIF2IUCN	Enrichment of species data with IUCN, GBIF and ancillary sources
• Data Cubes	OGC Coverages for Open Data Cube
• BioConn	Tool for displaying habitat connectivity
Pilot 3: Air Quality	Using IoT data to improve air quality forecasting
• Data Processing	Documentation and code for the dataset.
• Cross Data Store	Metadata configuration for this dataset on the Cross Data Store
• RAINBOW Data	Air quality vocabularies published in the OGC RAINBOW hosted instance
Cross-Domain Components	Non-domain-specific components
• GDIM	Green Deal Information Model
• Data Harmonisation Pipelines	Data harmonisation pipelines to generate GDIM compliant data
• STA Generation Service	SensorThings API generation service from GDIM compliant data
• RAINBOW Lookup	Lookup widget for vocabularies published in the OGC RAINBOW hosted instance
• CSWV Annotator	Integrating OGC RAINBOW vocabularies and terms into other interfaces and systems
• Data Ingestion	IoT Sensor Ingestion Tools
• EDC MVDS	EDC Minimal Viable Dataspace with extensions/improvements in AD4GD
• Connector Best Practices	IDSA compliant Dataspace Connector designed for the AD4GD Dataspace
• STAPIus Best Practices	Sensor Things API plus (SATplus) best practices
• TAPIS	Tables from OGC APIs (TAPIS) - frontend tool
• Geonetwork Catalog Best Practices	Catalog solution for geospatial data
• Data Trustworthiness	A framework for documenting the lineage, uncertainty and quality of datasets

Figure 6: AD4GD GitHub home page (<https://github.com/AD4GD/>).

2.1 COMPONENT 1 – AUTOMATED INGESTION OF DATA FROM LOW-COST SENSORS

This sensor data ingestion tool was initially developed as a prototype to evaluate the feasibility of harvesting and aggregating data from multiple types of low-cost air quality sensor platforms⁸, which

⁸ In accordance with SOSA and other data models, we refer to 'sensor platform' as a device which may contain one or many 'sensor's (e.g. particulate sensor, temperature sensor, noise sensor). Thus a personal air quality monitoring device

publish their data in a range of formats and via different channels. It was not originally intended to take the component beyond this exploratory level, but it proved to be extremely useful for aggregating data from difference sensors and thus supporting the evaluation of sensor platforms' bias and consistency. Given the importance of the Trustworthiness Framework within the pilots and the GDDS, it was decided to further develop the system to allow easier integration of new sensor platform types, and to more closely integrate it with the GDIM by allowing the conceptual mappings for observables, units of measures and sampling procedure to be defined by the user and used for both ingestion and for documentation of the outgoing data. As a result, the tool is now usable for a wider range of IoT sensors and not restricted to air quality.

The initial development was motivated by the rapidly expanding market for personal and volunteer environmental sensors, and the fact that data access protocols and formats vary so widely across this evolving ecosystem. Commercial manufacturers commonly offer data hosting, and dashboards with visualisation and analysis tools for a user's own sensor platforms (see examples in Figure 7) but options for data download vary from email requests for zip files to interactive web page requests for csv download.

Figure 7: Examples of commercial dashboards hosting data for a customer's sensors, from Plume Flow (left) and Earthsense Zephyr (right).

Participatory science networks such as PurpleAir and Sensor.Community collate and expose all participants' data for viewing and download, but vary in their approach: for example, PurpleAir provides a data download tool underpinned by real-time and historical data access APIs, but limits the redistribution of that data using open-source software⁹, while Sensor.Community offers an API to access recent data, and an File Transfer Protocol (FTP) archive for historic data under the Open Database (OdbL) 1.0 licence to which users consent when registering their sensor platform. A notable deficiency among most available data access APIs is the lack of geospatial query and filtering functionality for users on these platforms. The AD4GD component implements spatial queries for IoT data based on bounding boxes which record the locations of static sensors or the range of daily observations for mobile sensors. This is an extremely useful feature when users wish to find and evaluate collocated sensors within the database, or to dynamically assess observations in comparison to other available data sources.

As documented in D6.1, the system carries out a daily harvesting to ingest data from registered sensor platforms (see Figure 8). Data is aggregated into a PostGIS database and the open-source system may be replicated and deployed on a variety of platforms (in our case we use AWS). By M18 of the project the system's data model allowed registration of instances of three types of sensor platform; the Plume Flow 2¹⁰,

or a measuring station is referred to in this text as a 'sensor platform' even though it is more colloquially called a 'sensor'.

⁹ <https://www2.purpleair.com/policies/terms-of-service>

¹⁰ <https://plumelabs.com/en/flow/>

EarthSense Zephyr¹¹ and Sensor.Community open source AirRohr kit¹². The data retrieval process is different for each of these three sensor platform types, ranging from web scraping to csv download. Therefore, while the addition of a new sensor platform type was simplified as far as possible, at the midpoint of the project some coding effort was still required from the user (see Deliverable D6.1 for more detail on the Factory method approach and the data storage strategy for mobile and static sensors).

ID	LOOKUP_ID	SERIAL_NUMBER	ACTIVE	STATIONARY_BOX	TIME_UPDATED	TYPE_NAME	ACTIONS
1	18749	02:00:00:00:48:45	Online	View on Map	null	Plume	Actions
2	814	814:Zephyr	Online	View on Map	12/08/2025, 01:00:00	Zephyr	Actions
3	60641.SDS011.60642.BME280	60641.SDS011.60642.BME280:SensorCommunity	Online	View on Map	01/04/2023, 01:00:00	SensorCommunity	Actions
4	274866.outside	zen_2020:PurpleAir	Online	View on Map	22/07/2025, 00:00:00	PurpleAir	Actions
5	163763	2020:AirGradient	Online	View on Map	19/08/2025, 01:00:00	AirGradient	Actions

Figure 8: Front-end of the application, showing examples of the different sensor platform types with specific instances.

The experimental data harvesting work from M1-M18 allowed early identification of issues with field naming, data formatting and conceptual confusion (see examples of file format variability in Figure 9). This highlighted the importance of a centralised semantic harmonisation for observable properties, units of measure and sampling/correction procedures.

¹¹ <https://www.earthsense.co.uk/zephyr>

¹² <https://sensor.community/en/sensors/airrohr/>

```

|sensor_id;sensor_type;location;lat;lon;timestamp;P1;durP1;ratioP1;
P2;durP2;ratioP2
43363;SDS011;40636;52.424;-1.948;2021-05-24T00:00:42;4.35;;;2.42;;
43363;SDS011;40636;52.424;-1.948;2021-05-24T00:03:08;3.28;;;2.22;;
43363;SDS011;40636;52.424;-1.948;2021-05-24T00:05:34;3.55;;;2.20;;
43363;SDS011;40636;52.424;-1.948;2021-05-24T00:08:01;3.88;;;2.10;;
43363;SDS011;40636;52.424;-1.948;2021-05-24T00:10:29;7.45;;;2.00;;
43363;SDS011;40636;52.424;-1.948;2021-05-24T00:12:58;4.18;;;1.90;;

timestamp,date,latitude,longitude                timestamp,"date (UTC)","NO2 (ppb)","VOC (ppb)","pm 10
1621846710,"2021-05-24 08:58:30",52.240204,-1.770364 (ug/m3)","pm 2.5 (ug/m3)","NO2 (Plume AQI)","VOC (Plume AQI)","
1621849406,"2021-05-24 09:43:26",52.240206,-1.770364 10 (Plume AQI)","pm 2.5 (Plume AQI)","pm 1 (ug/m3)","pm 1 (Plume
1621849782,"2021-05-24 09:49:42",52.240206,-1.770365 AQI)"
1621850230,"2021-05-24 09:57:10",52.240207,-1.770366 1621846700,"2021-05-24
1621850536,"2021-05-24 10:02:16",52.240207,-1.770366 08:58:20",0,61,144.59767,17.518475,0,5,140,35,8,21
1621850836,"2021-05-24 10:07:16",52.240209,-1.770368 1621846760,"2021-05-24
1621851149,"2021-05-24 10:12:29",52.240209,-1.770368 08:59:20",2,52,33.28648,5.523699,2,4,33,11,5,11
1621851503,"2021-05-24 10:18:23",52.240208,-1.77036

Timestamp(UTC),Timestamp(UTS),Timestamp(Local),814-Temp(C)-slotB,814-Humidity(%RH)-
slotB,814-NO2(ug/m3)-slotB,814-O3(ug/m3)-slotB,814-NO(ug/m3)-slotB,814-PM1(ug/m3)-
slotB,814-PM2.5(ug/m3)-slotB,814-PM10(ug/m3)-slotB,814-Ambient temp(C)-slotB,814-Ambient
humidity(%RH)-slotB,814-Ambient pressure(hPa)-slotB
"2023-06-26T19:15:00+00:00",1687806900,"2023-06-
26T20:15:00+0100",30.1,30.36,10.59,0,0,0,2.75,3.03,29.9,30.57,1005.3
"2023-06-26T19:30:00+00:00",1687807800,"2023-06-
26T20:30:00+0100" 30 00 20 41 10 71 0 0 0 2 75 3 03 29 9 30 57 1005 3

```

Figure 9: Examples of the raw data format from three different sensor platforms: Sensor Community AirRohr (top), Plume Flow (centre – NB, this has two separate files for locations and measurements) and Earthsense Zephyr (bottom). This illustrates the variation in field names for the same phenomena across sensor platforms.

Within the prototype database presented at M18, field names were harmonised using hard-coded lookup tables. Since then, the process by which new sensor platforms are registered has been made more generic and extended to allow users to map columns in a vendor-specific data stream to concepts from the GDIM (see Figure 10). These mappings are stored and published on request through the same API that delivers the data¹³ (see Figure 11 for an example of the resulting csv-w output). The resulting output is consistent with the field mappings used in components Sections 2.3, 2.4, and 2.5, and the resulting semantic annotations are interoperable with the outputs from those components.

This semantic uplift is achieved as follows: at the point of defining a new sensor platform type, the user sets up a mapping of the incoming fields (Figure 12) to predefined concepts. Each of these concepts is already linked to URIs from the GDIM model, which explains its meaning and maps to equivalent terms from other domain vocabularies. This extension has allowed us to add three new sensor platform types to the harvesting workflow: AirGradient Open Air¹⁴ and PurpleAir Zen¹⁵ and Flex¹⁶. This in turn has facilitated collocation experiments to demonstrate sensor bias and consistency, which are described in Section 3.3.

¹³ Example metadata request: https://rn3rb93aq5.execute-api.eu-west-2.amazonaws.com/prod/sensor-platform-type/sensor_metadata/5
¹⁴ <https://www.airgradient.com/outdoor/>
¹⁵ <https://www2.purpleair.com/products/purpleair-zen>
¹⁶ <https://www2.purpleair.com/products/purpleair-flex>

Figure 10: Database tables supporting the semantic enrichment and column mappings for a range of sensor platforms.

Concepts for observable properties and units of measure are stored in the tables seen on the left, and these can be assembled into a structured JSON object which is stored in the 'sensor_metadata' field of the table representing sensor platform types.

```
"@context": "http://www.w3.org/ns/csvw",
"tableSchema":{
  "columns":[
    {
      "name":"timestamp",
      "titles":{
        "en":"The UTC timestamp of the observation"
      },
      "propertyUrl":"http://www.w3.org/ns/sosa/resultTime",
      "datatype": "http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/OGC/0/UnixTime-template"
    },
    {
      "name":"PM1",
      "titles":{
        "en":"The amount of suspended particulates in the air with a diameter of 1 micrometer (µm) or less. This measure has been humidity-corrected"
      },
      "http://purl.org/linked-data/sdmx/2009/attribute#unitMeasure":{
        "@id":"http://qudt.org/vocab/unit/MicroGM-PER-M3",
        "rdfs:label":"micrograms per m3",
        "http://qudt.org/schema/qudt#symbol":"µg/m³"
      },
      "http://www.w3.org/ns/sosa/usedProcedure":{
        "@id":"https://w3id.org/ad4gd/air-quality/procedures/pm-humidity-correction"
      },
      "propertyUrl":"https://w3id.org/ad4gd/air-quality/properties/pm1.0",
      "datatype":"float"
    }
  ],
}
```

Figure 11: Subsection of the csv-w metadata which can be retrieved on demand, showing the characterisation of observable properties, units of measure (highlighted in green) and processing steps. Terms from the GDIM are highlighted in pink.

Figure 12: Interface allowing the user to map the properties and units of measure of incoming sensor platform data to agreed concepts.

Full details can be seen in the code repository and documentation at <https://github.com/AD4GD/Component-AirQualityDataIngestion>.

2.2 COMPONENT 2 – DATA CONNECTOR SOLUTIONS

During the first half of AD4GD, the work in this respect was focused on implementing a first version of an IDSA-compliant data connector, relying on the Eclipse Data Connector (EDC) software stack. This implementation enabled the project to design and deploy the AD4GD Dataspace during the second half of the project, where this implementation has been extended to support all the required features to build the AD4GD catalogue and the publication of the selected data sources available, covering also the federation of several connectors from other related projects to build the prototype of AD4GD’s Minimum Viable Dataspace (MVD).

As described in D4.3, AD4GD’s MVD now supports more interactions between provider and consumer tenants: first, the introduction of the federated catalogue component allows the registration of several

connectors, all acting both as data providers and consumers and allowing the dataset sharing among the registered partners; secondly, the inclusion of specific adaptors allow the definition and registration of several HTTP sources as EDC Assets, increasing the catalogue offered by AD4GD.

As a result of this, the MVD has been extended from supporting simple dataset transactions between a provider and a consumer, towards a federated catalogue with several connectors sharing assets, as shown in Figure 13.

Figure 13: Federated connectors' scenario (extracted from D4.3)

In addition to the Federated Catalogue, the MVD also incorporates an Identity Provider using DAPS (Dynamic Attribute Provisioning Service), which is responsible for issuing and validating identity and access tokens. By incorporating a DAPS, the AD4GD Dataspace now enforces authenticated and trusted communication between connectors, ensuring that only verified participants can exchange data, which is a crucial step to align with security standards.

To populate this Federated Catalogue, a set of data sources generated in the context of AD4GD has been indexed, since several resources can be potentially converted into assets to be shared with other interested consumers, such as the datasets coming from the different pilots' implementations, which are stored in the AD4GD internal data repository. This repository is based on MinIO¹⁷, a high-performance Amazon S3-compatible object storage server suitable for AI/ML models, data lakes and database workloads. To adapt the EDC assets' definition capabilities to the S3 API requirements, a Python-based HTTP adaptor has been created to authenticate the AD4GD connector instance and configure the request. This adaptor is deployed as a container within the AD4GD cluster and exposed internally as an HTTP endpoint (reachable only by components deployed within the cluster). Once the negotiation process is finished, the asset is exposed through the Public API (AD4GD Connector's Public Endpoint). The process is summarized in Deliverable D4.3.

¹⁷ <https://min.io/>

Figure 14: AD4GD asset transfer process (extracted from D4.3).

In summary, deployment of the initial version of AD4GD EDC components was implemented in two nodes: a provider in ATOS premises/tenant and a consumer in PSNC premises/tenant. The components included the connector and the Web dashboard (called the “console”) that demonstrated a simple scenario of data transfer/exchange between these two nodes.

Deployment of the final AD4GD Dataspace demonstrator is a full Minimal Viable Data Space (MVDS) based on AD4GD EDC components, including:

- Web Data dashboards offer a user-friendly interface (UI), enabling users to manage connectors without the complexity of using the connector’s API directly.
- AD4GD Connectors are central elements of the Dataspace, providing secure, reliable, and structured data exchange between participants.
- Consumer backend extends the connector’s data plane by providing functionality to persist transferred assets into a user’s storage such as MinIO.
- Identity provider (DAPS) functions as an Identity Access Management (IAM) layer, issuing Dynamic Attribute Tokens (DAT) to authenticated and verified participants, ensuring secure and authenticated connections.
- Federated Catalogue functions as a data broker by enabling participants to find and access data offerings published by others

The final demonstrator includes 5 participant nodes, each acting as a consumer and provider, from 2 different projects:

- AD4GD cluster node
- PSNC node
- EOX – FAIRiCUBE node
- NILU – FAIRiCUBE node
- RASDAMAN – FAIRiCUBE node.

Details of the implementations are provided in Deliverables D4.2, D4.3, and D7.4 The component’s code is available on GitHub at <https://github.com/AD4GD/Component-AD4GD-DataConnector>.

2.3 COMPONENT 3 – SEMANTIC UPLIFT: SPARQL/JSON-LD FOR DATA EXCHANGE

One of main goals of AD4GD is to design and implement the building blocks to support a GDDS that will provide interoperability support for the heterogeneous and increasingly growing set of data and services available in the various action areas addressed by the GD through definition, sharing and assembly of standardised building blocks and that will directly contribute towards a European GDDS.

In order to enable different systems to exchange data with unambiguous meaning, and the provision of an integrated view over data from different (and heterogeneous) data sources, there is a need for an agreed common information model, or *lingua franca*, identifying and defining the data elements relevant to the application domain (i.e., Green Deal in case of AD4GD) along with their associated semantics/meaning for information exchange.

The AD4GD Green Deal Information Model (GDIM) is a common vocabulary aiming at providing the basis of a common GDDS and enabling the interoperability of different systems, potentially from different vendors. Based on the GDIM, data producers/integrators will be able to adapt and apply existing tools to pre-process, integrate and harmonize data from different sources; and service providers will be able to develop lightweight service wrappers and translators, also known as data providers and consumers, which will enable the different tools/platforms to expose and consume data in an interoperable form.

GDIM has been designed and implemented following a modular approach in a layered architecture. Based on the analysis of the state of the art and the initial analysis of the modelling requirements, GDIM is implemented by reusing and building partially over the Agriculture Information Model (AIM), which in turn reuses and aligns various relevant cross-domain standard ontologies and vocabularies, particularly from OGC and W3C. AIM is currently in the process of becoming an OGC standard.

The AD4GD Information Model defines the following layers:

- the meta-model layer, defining the model building blocks and enabling the back-and-forth conversion between datasets that are based on the property graph model and linked data datasets;
- the cross-domain layer, defining relevant concepts and properties that are common across multiple domains, and enabling the interoperability with existing standard models and vocabularies;
- the domain layer defining European Green Deal related concepts and properties covering different aspects of interest of GD applications, and enabling the integration of relevant vocabularies in the area;
- the pilot-specific layer defining additional concepts and properties that are of specific use for particular applications (if needed);
- a metadata model layer that can be used to describe datasets, services or applications in AD4GD.

GDIM is realised as a suite of OWL ontologies¹⁸ (serialised as RDF Turtle¹⁹), establishing alignments between the reused standards and well-scoped dominant models to enable their interoperability and the integration of existing data. From these ontologies, other related semantic artefacts are generated, including JSON-LD contexts and SHACL shapes²⁰, to facilitate the adoption by service developers/providers, and the validation of data at the semantic level, respectively.

¹⁸ <https://www.w3.org/OWL/>

¹⁹ <https://www.w3.org/TR/turtle/>

²⁰ <https://www.w3.org/TR/shacl/>

Details of the GDIM implementation are provided in Deliverables D1.3, D1.4, and are published in Semantic Interoperability in Data Spaces 2024 workshop²¹. The component's code is available on GitHub at <https://github.com/AD4GD/HarmonisationPipelines>, <https://github.com/AD4GD/GDIM>, and <https://github.com/AD4GD/STA-GenerationService>.

2.4 COMPONENT 4 – MOBILISING DATA TO STAPLUS

TAPIS is a lightweight multipurpose tool which can be utilised in following ways:

- Exploring APIs and services such as SensorThings API (STA), STApplus, S3, Eclipse Dataspace Connector, Catalogue Service for the Web (CSW) and OGC API collections, features, records and STAC. TAPIS is designed as a middle-ground solution between a URL based query interface such as Postman or curl and specialised domain-specific GUIs. This makes TAPIS an essential tool for conducting interoperability tests on newly developed or deployed services and API server instances.
- Direct reading of CSV, DBF, GeoPackage, JSON, JSON-LD and GeoJSON file formats. TAPIS is also a table editor, capable of selecting, filtering, merging, adding grouping, sorting, pivoting and semantically enrich tabular information. A part of a classical rows and columns tabular representation, data can be presented as bar charts, pie charts, scatter plots, and maps. TAPIS is integrated with NiMMbus (MiraMon implementation of the Geospatial User Feedback) and with the MiraMon Map Browser.

While the TAPIS tool was described in other deliverables (D3.2 and D4.3), this section focuses on listing the capacities that were developed for and were useful in this project. These characteristics converted the tool in a transversal client useful to test, access and visualize the data managed by most of the components of the AD4GD architecture. In that respect it was also useful in the Pilot cases (in particular Pilots 1 and 2) to verify the consistency of the data offered. TAPIS tool is useful to:

- access the federated catalogue in the Eclipse Data Connector and test the accessibility of the data available in the Dataspace (component 2). TAPIS was able to negotiate the contract, request the data and, if the format was compatible (CSV, JSON, etc.) show it in the screen as tables.
- visualize the semantic enriched JSON-LD (files that are annotated in a way that not many off-the-shelf tools support) tables which can be easily understood (Component 3).
- explore the data imported in the STA instance (Component 5) and visualize as graphics or maps. STA has a model that consist of a few objects linked together and the extraction of the data necessary for a particular application involves the generation of URL with some parameters (such as, \$filter, \$expand, etc) that is not easy to do manually. TAPIS facilitates this task.
- explore the content of the Open Data Cube exposed as a OGC API Coverages (Component 6). In this case TAPIS is able to explore the OGC APIs and determine the collections present.
- explore and visualize the GBIF export files with species occurrences data (that are in CSV format) and its semantically tagged version (Component 6)
- visualize the water modelling predictions and compare them with the original data (Component 8). The water predictions are also JSON-LD semantically enriched files.
- explore the metadata in the CSW catalogue (Component 9). The implementation extracts records of the GeoNetwork catalogue and presents every distribution (metadata about accessing the data) as a new row of the visualization table.
- visualize CSVW (semantic annotated CSVs) generated by the CSVW annotator (Component 12). The meaning of the columns of the data is presented as titles that links to the vocabulary term.

²¹ <https://semantic.internationaldataspaces.org/wp-content/uploads/2024/08/AD4GD-semantic-interoperability-approach-for-a-Green-Deal-Data-Space.pdf>

Figure 15: AD4GD asset in the MinIO data repository being accessed, interpreted as JSON-LD and presented as a table.

Details of the implementation are provided in Deliverables D3.2 and D4.3. The open-source code of TAPIS can be found on GitHub at <https://github.com/AD4GD/Component-TAPIS>. An official deployment can be found ready to use here: <https://www.tapis.grumets.cat>.

2.5 COMPONENT 5 – MOBILISING SENSOR DATA WITH STA

The IoT multi-protocol parser as a service was implemented in the context of the AD4GD WP3. In a nutshell, the IoT multi-protocol parser as a service receives the data generated by the heterogeneous IoT sensors through a given IoT communication protocol in a particular data format and converts the data to another IoT communication protocol and the related data format. A good example is the measurements done in the small lakes located in the city of Berlin: different types of IoT sensors provide the data related to the water level and quality under the form of CSV files published through the Berlin Wasserportal. The IoT multi-protocol parser as a service is able to retrieve the CSV files for a given period of time and converts these CSV files into JSON files following the specification and the data model elaborated during the AD4GD project, namely the OGC SensorThings API specification and the related data model. The resulting JSON files are sent to an instance of a FROST/STApplus server for storage. Other components or building blocks of the GDDS architecture proposed by the AD4GD project can read the IoT data from the FROST/STApplus server through the OGC SensorThings API.

The different elements of the IoT multi-protocol parser as a service are available on the dedicated GitHub source code repository:

- The FROST/STApplus server: https://github.com/AD4GD/Component-STApplus_Server
- Scripts using the OGC SensorThings API: <https://github.com/AD4GD/STA-Scripts>
- Conversion of the CSV files from the Berlin Wasserportal into STA requests: <https://github.com/AD4GD/pilot-1-BerlinWasserPortal>
- Ingestion of Weid Aqua 100 water quality sensor data in a FROST/STApplus server instance: <https://github.com/AD4GD/pilot-1-water-quality-ingestion>
- Firmware for mbed boards (commonly-used IoT components) with OGC SensorThings API: <https://github.com/AD4GD/mbed-sensorthings>

Further details are provided in Deliverable D3.2.

2.6 COMPONENT 6 – CATA CUBES FOR CONSUMING, PUBLISHING AND PROCESSING MULTIDIMENSIONAL DATA

2.6.1 OGC API COVERAGES FROM OPENDATACUBE

For Pilot 2, a Python tool (in the form of stand-alone code which is auto-executed through HTTPS requests) has been developed to generate Open Data Cube (ODC) OGC API Coverages. This supplements the existing access options such as Jupyter notebooks using Python or R implementations of the openEO package.

The tool itself can be operated from here: <https://callus.ddns.net/cgi-bin/mmdc.py>, and subsequent request conventions are given in footnotes. While following OGC API Coverages specifications, the user can access the collections stored in the ODC²². Once the collection is known, the specifications for a particular one can be accessed.²³ User can also access a particular collection from the ODC selecting by particular properties (e.g. time, space or other dimensions of the ODC)²⁴

Results from the query to the ODC can be obtained in COG or other formats such as PNG or JPG (by adding the parameters *&f=png* or *&f=jpeg* to the request or by HTTP content negotiation).

Knowing the syntax, the user can retrieve operations between layers, properties and times as complex as needed, thus helping the accessibility to the data.

In Figure 16, an NDVI is derived for a particular date and subset, using the request:

[https://callus.ddns.net/cgi-bin/mmdc.py/collections/s2_level2a_granule/coverage?subset=E\(422401.47:437401.47\),N\(4582942.45:4590742.45\),time\(%222018-03-29%22\)&properties=\(B08_10m-B04_10m\)/\(B08_10m%2BB04_10m\)](https://callus.ddns.net/cgi-bin/mmdc.py/collections/s2_level2a_granule/coverage?subset=E(422401.47:437401.47),N(4582942.45:4590742.45),time(%222018-03-29%22)&properties=(B08_10m-B04_10m)/(B08_10m%2BB04_10m))

Figure 16: NDVI image derived for a particular data and subset.

²² <https://callus.ddns.net/cgi-bin/mmdc.py/collections>

²³ https://callus.ddns.net/cgi-bin/mmdc.py/collections/s2_level2a_granule

²⁴ [https://callus.ddns.net/cgi-bin/mmdc.py/collections/s2_level2a_granule/coverage?subset=E\(422401.47:437401.47\),N\(4582942.45:4590742.45\),time\(%222018-04-28%22\)&subset-crs=\[EPSG:32631\]&crs=\[EPSG:32631\]&properties=\(B04_10m\)](https://callus.ddns.net/cgi-bin/mmdc.py/collections/s2_level2a_granule/coverage?subset=E(422401.47:437401.47),N(4582942.45:4590742.45),time(%222018-04-28%22)&subset-crs=[EPSG:32631]&crs=[EPSG:32631]&properties=(B04_10m))

Figure 17 shows retrieval of NDVI for the same particular time and subset, but only when the LULC band category is 6 (or forest):

[http://callus.ddns.net/cgi-bin/mmdc.py/collections/s2_level2a_granule/coverage?subset=E\(422401.47:437401.47\),N\(4582942.45:4590742.45\),time\(%222018-04-28%22\)&subset-crs=\[EPSG:32631\]&crs=\[EPSG:32631\]&properties=\(B08_10m-B04_10m\)/\(B08_10m%2BB04_10m\)-Slice\(%27\(B08_10m-B04_10m\)/\(B08_10m%2BB04_10m\)%27,\[%27time%27\],\[%272018-04-18%27\]\)&filter=\(SCL_20m=4\)%20or%20\(SCL_20m=5\)%20or%20\(SCL_20m=6\)](http://callus.ddns.net/cgi-bin/mmdc.py/collections/s2_level2a_granule/coverage?subset=E(422401.47:437401.47),N(4582942.45:4590742.45),time(%222018-04-28%22)&subset-crs=[EPSG:32631]&crs=[EPSG:32631]&properties=(B08_10m-B04_10m)/(B08_10m%2BB04_10m)-Slice(%27(B08_10m-B04_10m)/(B08_10m%2BB04_10m)%27,[%27time%27],[%272018-04-18%27])&filter=(SCL_20m=4)%20or%20(SCL_20m=5)%20or%20(SCL_20m=6))

Figure 17: NDVI for the same date and subset, restricted to the 'forest' class of the LULC map.

One could use other layers from the same ODC as filters, thus crossing information from different layers, bands or times.

More details about this tool in here: https://github.com/AD4GD/Component-OAPI_CoveragesForODC

2.6.2 ECMWF DATACUBE

On the other hand, Pilot 3 includes a dedicated data cube generation pipeline that transforms irregularly spaced IoT sensor measurements into harmonized 3D spatiotemporal data cubes with consistent resolution in latitude, longitude, and time. This is achieved through a kriging-based observation operator applied to quality-checked and machine learning-corrected time series.

All outputs are gridded at 0.01° resolution and available at hourly and daily intervals from 2018 to 2024. The entire pipeline is implemented in PyTorch,²⁵ enabling efficient, GPU-accelerated processing. These data cubes form the core observational layer for various scientific and operational use cases. Further details, including figures and methodology, are provided in the Pilot 3 section and Deliverable D4.3.

²⁵ <https://pytorch.org/>

End user access to this datacube is provided by the recently-developed Cross Data Store (XDS)²⁶, which provides a user interface (see Figure 18) that allows users to sub-select along axes of the datacube before downloading that selection. Like other datacube access solutions, this makes it feasible to host very large datacubes whilst still providing reasonably sized downloads to end users.

The screenshot shows a web interface for data selection with the following filters:

- Type:** Combined IoT + CAMS, Only IoT data
- Variable:** Particulate matter d < 2.5 µm (PM2.5), Particulate matter d < 10 µm (PM10)
- Frequency:** Daily, Hourly
- Year:** 2018, 2019, 2020, 2021, 2022, 2023, 2024
- Month:** January, February, March, April, May, June, July, August, September, October, November, December
- Day:** A grid of days from 01 to 31, all of which are selected with checkboxes.

Figure 18: The data download tab from the XDS page for the Pilot 3 data.²⁷

2.7 COMPONENT 7 – OPEN WORKFLOWS FOR HABITAT CONNECTIVITY COMPUTATION

The following component consists of several subcomponents, which represent related workflows, exchanging data to achieve a flexible and scalable solution to calculate habitat connectivity at local and regional scales.

2.7.1 DATA4LAND

This software explores how input land-use/land-cover (LULC) datasets can be enhanced with other data, including the OpenStreetMap (OSM) database, the World Database on Protected Areas (WDPA), and expert-knowledge-based ecological parameters of target species. Data4Land utilises three APIs (Overpass Turbo, Ohsome, and Protected Planet), builds queries from the user-defined configuration, and fetches data for the area of interest, covering regional or local extents. For the pilot area, it has been decided to use the OSM database instead of the open regional data provided by the Catalonian administration, as the latter lack

²⁶ <https://xds-dev.ecmwf.int/datasets/derived-air-quality>

²⁷ <https://xds-dev.ecmwf.int/datasets/derived-air-quality?tab=download>

many human-built objects and water ways. The output data can be used further in the next two components, or for other purposes, such as analysis of land cover dynamics, modelling of land use changes, spatial planning, delineation of water features, and water basin mapping.

The component's code and documentation is available on GitHub at Data4Land <https://github.com/AD4GD/pilot-2-preprocessing>, and is published in the SoftwareX journal (Kriukov et al, 2025).

2.7.2 CONTAINERISED GRAPHAB APPLICATION

Graphab v3.0 is software to evaluate the landscape connectivity of habitats (for further detail, see Deliverable D6.1, section 4.6.1). It uses LULC data and a landscape impedance matrix, provided by the user, to create geospatially referenced data on connectivity levels across habitat patches or between them. It has been deployed as a containerised application on the ATOS Kubernetes cluster with automatic ingestion of ASTON and CREA data from the MinIO object storage. The application contains several commands, which calculate connectivity indices relevant to Pilot 2, along with post-processing block to extract statistics and build charts illustrating connectivity dynamics from 1987 to 2022, which varies across connectivity indices, habitats, and case study extents.

This sub-component's code and documentation is available on GitHub at <https://github.com/AD4GD/pilot-2-biodiversity/tree/main/graphab>.

2.7.3 MIRAMON PROCESSING

MiraMon is another commonly used tool to evaluate landscape connectivity through the Index of Terrestrial Connectivity (ICT). In contrast to Graphab, it produces only one index per pair of input landscape impedance and affinity datasets. However, it is similar in that the user should provide calculation parameters (distance between sample points and exploration radius from points). This sub-component describes Shell and batch scripts to produce ICT raster outputs (for the detailed description of Miramon under-the-hood processing, see Deliverables 6.1, section 4.6.1 and the official MiraMon documentation). The performance of this tool has been improved during AD4GD project.

This sub-component's code and documentation is available on GitHub at <https://github.com/AD4GD/miramon> as well as <https://www.miramon.cat/help/eng/msa/ICT.htm>

2.7.4 GBIF2IUCN

This tool is developed to enrich the custom list of species provided by user with tabular data from Global Biodiversity Information Framework (GBIF), IUCN Red List of Threatened species, and other Red Lists, such as the Red List of Spain (Listado de Especies Silvestres en Régimen de Protección Especial y del Catálogo Español de Especies Amenazadas), and the Red List of Catalonia (Espècies protegides i amenaçades de la fauna autòctona a Catalunya). It includes operations for fixing scientific names of species, retrieving unique keys of species from all databases (including REST services from the Global Biodiversity Data Viewer, developed by the EU Joint Research Centre), fetching multiple columns from tables, and accessing GBIF occurrence data cubes for target species to produce a raster dataset with the estimated number of species occurrences per pixel.

This sub-component's code and documentation is available on GitHub at [GBIF2IUCN https://github.com/AD4GD/pilot-2-gbif-iucn/tree/main](https://github.com/AD4GD/pilot-2-gbif-iucn/tree/main).

2.7.5 BIODIVERSITY ML

This sub-component utilises an image-to-image conditional generative adversarial network machine learning model, Pix2Pix, to produce the Index of Terrestrial connectivity (see MiraMon Processing sub-component) for custom land-use/land-cover datasets. The model is trained with the MiraMon tool results.

The developed models improve time performance by up to 1,900 times for high-resolution (30m, 8651x8981 pixels) raster datasets and 110-130 times for low-resolution (390m, 655x690) datasets, significantly accelerating habitat connectivity calculations (for further details, please see Deliverable D5.2, section 2.2.1). Through training and steady model improvement, this subcomponent is capable of producing high-quality outputs for connectivity of two habitat types – forest and aquatic. The effect of high-resolution ground-truth data is particularly important, as this model produces much more accurate outputs compared to low-resolution ground-truth data, with global mean squared errors of 0.064 and 0.194 respectively.

Additionally, the developed sub-component includes post-processing, as original images are sliced for computational efficiency before model training and inference, while output images should be reconstructed. The models are also exposed through a REST API to be used by end users of the Bioconn graphical user-interface tool in an on-demand way, when calculating connectivity dynamics for land cover change scenarios (see Deliverables 5.2, section 3.2.2).

Each of the tools is explored in detail in Section 3 (Pilot 2). Details of the implementation are provided in Deliverables D5.2, D6.1, and the code is available on github at the URLs specified in each sub-section above.

2.8 COMPONENT 8 – WATER MODELLING AND PREDICTION

2.8.1 MACHINE LEARNING FOR WATER AVAILABILITY PREDICTION

Pilot 1, as outlined in Deliverables D5.1 and D5.2, used AI and ML to support conservation efforts and assess drought risks in Berlin's lakes. With over 300 small urban lakes, Berlin faces growing water availability challenges due to climate change, extreme weather, and urbanization. These lakes are ecologically and socially valuable, contributing to biodiversity, climate regulation, and flood prevention. Understanding and predicting water availability is therefore crucial for the city's environmental resilience and quality of life.

The goal of WP5 in this context is to develop AI/ML models that forecast water availability based on historical weather and lake data, particularly focusing on the impact of precipitation on water levels. Data was sourced from Wasserportal Berlin (for water and groundwater levels) and Open-Meteo (for weather data). Given the time-dependent nature of the data, the problem was approached as a time series forecasting task, and three model types were evaluated: ARIMA (Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average), SARIMA (Seasonal Autoregressive Integrated Moving Average), and LSTM (Long Short-Term Memory). In the end, LSTM was chosen over ARIMA and SARIMA due to its ability to capture long-term dependencies, handle non-linear relationships, adapt to changing environmental patterns, and deliver better forecasting performance with complex, large datasets, making it well-suited for the environmental time series data in Pilot 1. In D6.1 it was reported that the initial ML pipeline was a time series prediction for the water level for a given lake. The initial implementation used only water level data; since then, this implementation has been refined: first, weather data was also introduced into the pipeline, tailoring these input data to each of the lakes. As outlined in D5.2, the model has been enhanced to support recursive forecasting, which means that it can predict future water levels step by step, using its own previous predictions as input for the next time steps. To effectively integrate water level and weather data, three forecasting scenarios have been established:

- **Predicted precipitation scenario:** Forecasts future water levels using anticipated precipitation data.
- **Zero precipitation scenario:** Assumes no upcoming rainfall, simulating a drought or worst-case scenario.
- **High precipitation scenario:** Simulates extreme weather by assuming a constant, elevated level of rainfall. This threshold is customized for each lake, set at 75% of the historical maximum recorded precipitation.

As mentioned before, all this has been implemented in a ML pipeline according to the ML lifecycle defined in Deliverable D5.1, and represented here in Figure 19:

- Raw incoming data is first stored in MinIO. This triggers an MQTT notification, which automatically launches the data harmonization tool developed in WP1 (further explained in Section 4.2).
- The harmonized data produced by this tool is also saved in MinIO.
- Once the harmonized dataset is ready, it is fed into the prediction model, which is deployed via KServe.
- The model generates forecasted values, which are again stored in MinIO.
- These predictions are then available for use by any relevant stakeholders.

The pipeline runs weekly, in line with the frequency at which new pilot 1 data becomes available in MinIO.

Figure 19: Pilot 1 ML Model's inferencing schema (extracted from D5.2).

A thorough analysis of the results of the different models is presented in D5.2, together with some potential future research lines to pursue after AD4GD's conclusion. Readers are encouraged to consult this document for further information regarding AI/ML models developed in the context of AD4GD.

Details of the implementation are provided in Deliverables D5.1 and D5.2.

2.8.2 OPENEO DATA HARVESTING FOR WATER QUALITY ESTIMATION

Within Pilot 1, an index of water quality was developed and evaluated in the form of the "normalized difference trophic index" (NDTrI) which is described in more detail in Section 3.1.1, and in the AD4GD publication Zamzow et al., 2025. Initial experiments on computing lake trophic state were carried out in Google Earth Engine (see Deliverable D6.1) but as the project progressed it was possible to migrate this code to EU infrastructure and to make use of the Copernicus Data Space Ecosystem to compute this index using Sentinel-2 data.

The entire data processing workflow, from download to pixel-specific NDTrI calculation, is part of the AD4GD project and can be found in the project's GitHub repository. The available Jupyter Notebook implements a job to be performed on the OpenEO platform. Once the job is finished, the data is downloaded in GeoTIFF or netCDF format. The job involves the following steps:

- Filter for a bounding box.
- Definition of a time period.

- Filter for the bands 2, 5 and the Scene Classification Band (SCL).
- Use of all pixels in the bounding box that are classified as water by SCL to more than 80% after the scenes of previous clouds, cloud shadows, snow, and topographical shadows have been removed.
- These pixels are calculated into an NDTrI_image whenever they are identified as water. The NDTrI per pixel is defined as $NDTrI_{image} = \frac{B5-B2}{B5+B2}$.
- The NDTrI image values are then first summarized as monthly averages and finally as seasonal averages.

The usage and integration of this component is further described in Section 3.1.1. The code and documentation can be accessed at <https://github.com/AD4GD/Component-openEO-harvester/>

2.9 COMPONENT 9 – DATA CATALOGUE AND METADATA

At this final stage of the project, the AD4GD GeoNetwork catalogue includes 39 metadata records distributed across the three pilot domains as detailed in Table 1.

Table 1: Summary of metadata records by pilot domain.

Pilot ID	Pilot domain	Number of metadata records
Pilot 1	Water	23
Pilot 2	Biodiversity	9
Pilot 3	Air Quality	10
Total		42

The distribution of metadata records across the three pilots responds to the different characteristics and spatial scales of the respective study areas, deriving in different strategies for metadata documentation. In Pilot 1 (Water), which focuses on the monitoring of small lakes in the city of Berlin, metadata was organized mainly at the lake level, with each metadata record in GeoNetwork corresponding to a group of datasets associated with a specific lake (with some exceptions). By contrast, in Pilot 2 (Biodiversity) and Pilot 3 (Air Quality), the metadata was structured at the dataset level, with each metadata record representing a different dataset relevant to the thematic scope and to the regional (Catalonia) and continental (Europe) geographical extents respectively. An overview of the GeoNetwork catalogue is provided in Figure 20.

Figure 20: Overview of AD4GD GeoNetwork metadata.

As part of the semantic efforts to make metadata more informative, keywords in ISO19115 metadata are linked to standard vocabularies unique URL, starting from the Essential Variables (EVs) terms hosted on the OGC RAINBOW Definitions Server (<https://defs-hosted.opengis.net/prez-hosted/catalogs/hosted:ad4gd>) for the three pilot domains. This linkage is performed by using the <gmx:Anchor> element inside of the <gmd:keyword> element of the ISO19115/19139 XML metadata file. The result is presented in GeoNetwork as clickable items that redirect to the individual definition of the keyword published in OGC RAINBOW (Figure 21).

Figure 21: Visual result of an encoded EV as ISO19115 linkable keyword in XML, its appearance in GeoNetwork and the EV as published in OGC RAINBOW.

Some examples of RAINBOW concepts linked to GeoNetwork keywords include:

- Water level: <https://w3id.org/ad4gd/water-quality/properties/water-level>
- Water temperature: <https://w3id.org/ad4gd/water-quality/properties/water-temperature>
- Species distributions of terrestrial mammals binary presence absence: http://w3id.org/ad4gd/ev/ebv/SP_dis_TER_mammals_BPA
- Ecosystem distribution of terrestrial ecosystem habitat types: http://w3id.org/ad4gd/ev/ebv/ES_edis_TER_ecosystemHabitatTypes_OCM_Prod1

The GeoNetwork ISO19115 metadata collection is considered the master copy of the metadata used and produced in AD4GD project. While data are also published in the EDC federated catalogue as DCAT assets (see Section Component 2), they initially included only minimal metadata, omitting the richer GeoNetwork content. To address this, PSNC implemented an interoperable solution that enabled the propagation of metadata to the EDC catalogue from GeoNetwork.

Each GeoNetwork record has one or more associated data distributions (e.g. in MinIO, FROST, or ODC). Each distribution is created as an individual asset in the EDC catalogue. The GeoNetwork metadata was added in the property “metadata” of the JSON-LD asset description (the minimum metadata that EDC provides by default). In practice, the resulting metadata is a DCAT/Dublin core conversion of the original ISO19115. An example is shown in Figure 22.

Figure 22: DCAT/Dublin core conversion of the original ISO19115.

This approach allows us to demonstrate that the AD4GD node of the Dataspace can produce metadata in the same format that the EDC implements and the IDSA recommends. GeoNetwork catalogue is a broadly system used to document environmental data (as in Europe with the INSPIRE) in the geospatial domain and could maintain a role within the GDDS.

Details of the implementation are provided in Deliverables D4.2 and D4.3. Component’s code is available on GitHub at <https://github.com/AD4GD/Component-GeoNetwork>. AD4GD GeoNetwork catalogue is available at <https://catalogue.grumets.cat/geonetwork/ad4gd>.

In addition, data relevant to AD4GD is also documented in EDC catalogue. Consumer Dashboard (PSNC) that is available at <https://consumer-dashboard-edc-connector.apps.dcw1.paas.psncl.pl>; Provider Dashboard (ATOS) is also available at <https://ad4gd-dash-edc.dashboard-siba.store>.

2.10 COMPONENT 10 – DATA CATALOGUE AND METADATA WITH SEMANTIC UPLIFT

Deliverable D6.1 proposed the development of a component to extract and transform metadata from GeoNetwork into a semantically compatible format, specifically GeoDCAT. The motivation behind this was to enable the integration of heterogeneous data catalogues—whether based on GeoNetwork, other ISO 19115 implementations, or systems capable of producing DCAT/GeoDCAT metadata—into a unified, queryable "virtual super-catalogue".

To explore the feasibility of this approach, an experimental pipeline was developed. This prototype involved:

1. Crawling a GeoNetwork instance via its API to retrieve dataset metadata in ISO 19115 (XML) format.
2. Transforming the retrieved XML documents into GeoDCAT, in our case using an XSLT transform.
3. Uploading the resulting RDF to a triplestore for semantic querying.

The XSLT used in this process was developed by a third party in the context of a different project and was tailored specifically to GeoDCAT-AP, the European application profile of GeoDCAT. While this allowed for a working proof-of-concept, successfully demonstrated on the AD4GD catalogue hosted by CREA, the approach revealed several limitations:

- Tight coupling to GeoDCAT-AP: The XSLT was heavily customized for GeoDCAT-AP, including the use of specific controlled vocabularies (e.g., for subject terms), which limited its generalizability. Enhancing or adapting the transformation logic proved challenging due to the inherent complexity and rigidity of XSLT, especially when trying to support alternative vocabularies or metadata profiles.
- Limited reusability: The component was closely tied to the structure and configuration of the AD4GD GeoNetwork instance. Adapting it to other catalogues would require significant effort, particularly in remapping controlled vocabularies and metadata fields.
- Existing GeoNetwork support for DCAT: GeoNetwork already offers a built-in DCAT export, although it covers only a limited subset of the DCAT specification. This raised questions about the added value of maintaining a separate transformation pipeline.
- Emerging standards: ISO is currently developing ISO 19115-4, a JSON serialization of the ISO 19115 metadata model. This new format is expected to be more amenable to transformation into semantic formats like [Geo]DCAT, using modern tooling such as JSON-LD transformers and without the constraints of XML/XSLT.

Given these factors, it was concluded that the development of a full-fledged GeoNetwork-to-GeoDCAT transformation component fell outside the practical scope of the AD4GD project. While the experimental work demonstrated technical feasibility, the approach was not sustainable or generalizable enough to justify further investment within the project timeline.

Component's code is available on GitHub at <https://github.com/ogcincubator/iso19115-to-geodcat>.

2.11 COMPONENT 11 – DATA TRUSTWORTHINESS FRAMEWORK

The Data Trustworthiness Framework developed in WP4 informs and was informed by work in each of the three pilots.

For example, pilot 3 ensures the reliability of low-cost sensor data by combining rule-based filtering with machine learning correction. It identifies implausible values, filters outliers using comparisons with CAMS forecasts, and groups sensors into spatial clusters using the OPTICS algorithm. A supervised correction model based on XGBoost adjusts remaining time series for known biases using meteorological

inputs and seasonal indicators. This process produces harmonised, quality-controlled data that form the basis for subsequent gridding and data cube generation.

Details of the technical implementation are provided in Deliverables D4.2 and D4.3 for pilot 3 as well as for pilot 1 and 2. The component's code is available on GitHub at <https://github.com/AD4GD/Component-Data-Trustworthiness-Framework>.

2.12 COMPONENT 12 – GDIM SEMANTIC TERMS - RAINBOW SERVER

After several discussions with pilots and technical partners, it was clear that existing vocabularies/thesauri of observable properties (e.g., air and water quality variables) and observation procedures were only able to partially cover the needs of the pilots, as they were in many cases either not specific enough or too specific, and slightly different than the actual property observed. Accordingly, it was decided to define own vocabularies/taxonomies in the different pilots and make whenever possible alignment with standard vocabularies. A similar approach was taken for modelling relevant sensors and platforms with their related manufacturers.

Additionally, AD4GD generated the semantic representation of Essential Agriculture Variables (EAV) and Essential Biodiversity Variables (EBV). During the last period of the project, the conceptualisation of the EBVs description was updated to follow the I-ADOPT ontology. This transformation is carried out via a semantic uplift pipeline (using the data harmonization tools). In addition to the adoption of I-ADOPT to represent EBV, the semantic representation of Essential Climate Variables (ECVs) was created, although not based on I-ADOPT framework. All of these vocabularies have been published and are available in OGC RAINBOW server.

Details of the implementation are provided in Deliverable D1.4. Component's code is available on GitHub at

- <https://github.com/AD4GD/GDIM/tree/main/AD4GD-vocabularies>
- <https://github.com/AD4GD/pilot-1-water-quality/tree/master/rainbow-data>
- <https://github.com/AD4GD/pilot-2-biodiversity/tree/main/rainbow-data>
- <https://github.com/AD4GD/pilot-3-air-quality/tree/main/rainbow-data>

2.12.1 OGC RAINBOW IMPROVEMENTS

To enhance the semantic processing and publication of the GDIM and the AD4GD controlled vocabularies, significant improvements and developments were implemented throughout the project:

- The semantic publishing layer of the OGC RAINBOW system was extensively updated and tailored to project needs. Enhancements included improved data visualization, optimized performance, responsive design for mobile devices, expanded support for a broader range of semantic resources (beyond SKOS-based models), and more robust profile handling, among other refinements.
- The OGC Data Exchange toolkit also underwent substantial upgrades. New functionalities were introduced to support semantic data transformation, enrichment and annotation, provenance tracking, and data validation, further strengthening its capabilities for interoperable and trustworthy data exchange.

2.12.2 RAINBOW LOOKUP

The RAINBOW lookup component is an embeddable HTML element that allows users to find and select concepts from a OGC RAINBOW instance.

It provides a user interface that can be employed in metadata definition or item categorization systems. For example, it can be included as part of larger web-based applications when there is a need to retrieve concepts from controlled vocabularies.

The source code of the component is published on GitHub under the Apache License version 2.0. There is a demo page²⁸ available with examples on how to integrate it in other projects (Figure 23).

Figure 23: Demo page with the RAINBOW Lookup component in action.

JavaScript RAINBOW Lookup code is available at <https://github.com/ogcincubator/rainbow-lookup> and <https://ogcincubator.github.io/rainbow-lookup/>. A live demo is available at: <https://github.com/AD4GD/rainbow-lookup>.

2.12.3 CSVW ANNOTATOR

The CSVW annotator is a web interface designed to simplify the creation of CSV on the Web (CSVW) definitions.

Comma-separated values (CSV) files are used across many different applications due to the simplicity of their format, where data rows are laid out as a series of entries or cells separated by a delimiter character (usually a comma), optionally quoted, and encoded as strings of characters (one line per row). However, the format lacks any formal means to attach metadata or define the characteristics of the columns, let alone semantically annotate them.

CSVW²⁹ is a W3C-backed standard to semantically describe and annotate CSV files, using JSON-LD. The CSVW annotator component provides a user interface to aid in the task of creating these JSON-LD mapping documents.

Through this interface, users can load and preview a CSV file (Figure 24) and map its individual columns to terms in a series of controlled vocabularies hosted on an OGC RAINBOW system (Figure 25).

²⁸ <https://ad4gd.github.io/rainbow-lookup/>

²⁹ <https://csvw.org/>

Figure 24: Loading and previewing a file in the CSVW annotator.

Figure 25: Annotating CSVW columns with OGC RAINBOW terms.

Data types (e.g., string, boolean, integer...) can be declared for the fields, and fields can also be marked as being part of the dataset's "primary key" of the data. A CSVW document with all the mappings will be created by the application (Figure 26), which can later be applied to any files following the same column structure.

```
PREVIEW DATA  BINDINGS  RESULT

{
  "@context": "http://www.w3.org/ns/csvw",
  "tableSchema": {
    "columns": [
      {
        "name": "John",
        "propertyUrl": "https://w3id.org/ad4gd/air-quality/properties/pressure",
        "datatype": "float"
      },
      {
        "name": "Doe"
      },
      {
        "name": "120 jefferson st."
      },
      {
        "name": "Riverside"
      },
      {
        "name": " NJ"
      },
      {
        "name": " 08075"
      }
    ]
  },
  "dialect": {
    "header": true
  }
}
```

Figure 26: Resulting CSVW document.

CSVW Annotator code is available at <https://github.com/ogcincubator/csvw-rainbow> and <https://github.com/AD4GD/csvw-rainbow>. Live demo is available at <https://ogcincubator.github.io/csvw-rainbow>.

During AD4GD TAPIS also incorporated a tool to semantically annotate tables and exporting this semantics to CSVW. However, TAPIS is not able to connect to semantic vocabularies requiring the user to do it in its own way.

3 PILOTS

3.1 PILOT 1 – WATER QUALITY

The final status of this pilot, in terms of components, integration and data pipelines, is shown in Figure 27.

Figure 27: The above diagram shows the final workflow(s) for this pilot, highlighting the use of specific components (labelled by the section where they are described) and distinguishing elements which have been reused as-is (white), extended for re-use (orange) or developed within the project (green). To clarify progress since the reporting in D6.1, bold arrows are used to distinguish workflow steps integrated between M19-M36.

3.1.1 REMOTE SENSING DATA FOR THE ESTIMATION OF WATER QUALITY AND WATER AVAILABILITY

There are many COPERNICUS products based on Sentinel-2 data that determine water properties. These include, for example, turbidity, chlorophyll a content, and water level. However, to obtain water level data, the satellite must be positioned vertically above the lake, meaning that only thin tracks can be used rather than entire areas of the image. Because it is nearly impossible for these tracks to intersect small lakes, remote sensing data is not used to describe their water levels.

A new index has been developed that can estimate the trophic status of lakes. The biggest challenge was the limited number of pixels available on satellite images to describe small lakes. This makes using remote sensing for real-time measurements of chlorophyll a or turbidity very error-prone. Trophic status, on the other hand, is determined over the course of an entire growing season, which in Germany usually lasts from April to October. Instead of combining many spatially distributed pixels into an average value,

the idea is to use many temporally distributed pixels. This method was developed using 294 lakes greater than 50 hectares in Brandenburg, Germany, for which trophic data was available at three-year intervals. A single pixel on the lake surface was used to estimate the lake's trophic status. Satellite-based trophic estimation correlated between 0.83 and 0.92 with in-situ data in all five years using ground truth data. More detailed information on the validation and the method can be found in D4.2 and in the AD4GD publication Zamzow *et al.*, 2025.

The index is referred to as the "normalized difference trophic index" (NDTrI) and is calculated by combining the reflectances of bands 2 and 5 of the Sentinel-2 L2A product. The technical implementation of this processing using OpenEO has been described in Section 2.8.2, and involves filtering of the available EO data by location, time and data quality before a ratioing operation is applied and the results are aggregated by month and season.

Although only one pixel in each lake was used to validate the method, all pixels can be included to calculate a lake-wide average. The trophic status of a body of water can fluctuate significantly from one year to the next. However, these fluctuations are often due to external conditions. To calculate a robust status for Berlin's lakes, data from three years is combined. Alternatively, the lakes can be ranked each year. The relative nature of the comparison takes external fluctuations into account. Overall, this method was applied to 42 Berlin lakes large enough to be evaluated with Sentinel-2 data. Figure 28 shows the ranking of some lakes from 2018 to 2024. In order to generate the ranks shown in the cells of the figure, the lakes are divided into ten groups, with the first group consisting of the top 5%, and the tenth group consisting of the bottom 5% of lake water quality. The eight groups in between are equally sized percentile gradations between 5% and 95% of the total lake distribution based on NDTrI. This evaluation method provides a quick overview of how the lakes' water quality can be classified in relation to each other. For most lakes in Berlin, no clear trend has emerged over the past seven years. Lakes in a given group typically remain within that range, and vice versa. The lake with the strongest trend is Lietzensee (fifth row from the bottom). In 2021, it was in the ninth group, but it has since risen to the middle of the distribution. This makes sense, as several remediation measures have been implemented there in recent years. Therefore, this method can be used to evaluate the effects of such measures.

Figure 28: Classification of lakes according to their trophic state based on remote sensing.

3.1.2 CITIZEN SCIENCE AS LAKE MONITORING SUPPORT

The goal was to design the citizen science support in such a way that interested citizens could participate even without much experience or prior knowledge. Two different methods of data collection were developed. On the one hand, qualitative data can be collected via an app, and on the other hand, simple measurements of nutrients and conductivity are carried out using low-budget tests and sensors.

3.1.2.1 QUALITATIVE DATENERFASSUNG MITTELS APP

The CrowdWater app, which was designed and is maintained by the University of Zurich and developed by Spotteron, was used to collect data. The app, originally developed for small rivers, was further developed for use with small urban lakes. For this purpose, a questionnaire was created in close consultation with Berlin stakeholders. The questions relate to the categories of lake use, the lake as a biotope, water quality, and water availability. All questions and their possible answers are listed in Table 6 in Annex I. They are further integrated into the RAINBOW server, so that same observations can be done

independently of the CrowdWater app. A one-time registration is required to use the app. Data entry for a lake can be done in 18 different languages and takes about 3 to 5 minutes. All data from the app is freely available to registered users.

The AD4GD project then developed indicators for assessing water quality in terms of nutrients, biotope, use, and risk of water scarcity. The indicators are created by summarizing the answers to individual questions in a semi-quantitative manner. To this end, the answers are assigned plus or minus points, which are calculated for each indicator. For example, the answer “clear” to the question about water colour is given a +1 in the water quality assessment, while the colours ‘green’ or “brown” are given a -1. Not all questions are relevant for all indicators. The allocation of points per indicator and the calculation rule for the indicator are also given in Annex I.

Figure 29 to Figure 32 show the distribution of the four indicators in Berlin lakes.

Critical conditions can be easily detected using this representation. Lakes with extremely high nutrient levels are just as easy to identify as lakes with critical water shortages. However, the following limitations must be taken into account:

- The informative value is directly related to the number of observations made per lake. Since some characteristics are seasonal, it is desirable to have consistent observations throughout the year. However, for many of the lakes shown below, only one or two observations were made. The maps can therefore only be used as a rough guide at this stage.
- The indicators are based on strong simplifications. Particularly with regard to the indicator for biotopes, it should be noted that, due to the requirement for simplicity in data collection, much relevant information is not included. It describes the habitat requirements in very broad terms, but does not contain any information about specific species and is therefore not comparable with biotope descriptions based on species identification.

Figure 29: Distribution of the nutrient indicator of Berlin lakes.

Figure 30: Distribution of the biotope indicator of Berlin lakes.

Figure 31: Distribution of the lake usage indicator of Berlin lakes.

Figure 32: Distribution of the water stress indicator of Berlin lakes.

3.1.2.2 SIMPLE MEASUREMENTS BY WATER RANGERS AND STUDENTS

There are no measurements available for most of Berlin's small lakes. Since lake managers are unable to monitor all lakes regularly due to capacity constraints, the suitability of simple test procedures carried out by citizens to fill this knowledge gap was examined. The following tests were used and are stored in the Rainbow server as procedures:

- Phosphate Test: Easy Life PO₄ Phosphate Test Kit Water Quality Tests (range: 0.02 – 2 mg/L)
- Nitrite Test: JBL Pro Aquatest NO₂ Water Analysis (range: 0.01 – 1 mg/L)
- Nitrate Test: JBL Pro Aquatest NO₃ Water Analysis (range: 0.5 – 200 mg/L)
- Ammonium Test: JBL Pro Aquatest NH₄ Water Analysis (range: 0.05 – 5 mg/L)

All samples were taken at the lake shore. Since the tests are simple aquarium water tests, their validity for small urban lakes had to be verified. This was done by directly comparing the test results with cuvette tests from Hach-Lange. The data was compared in matrices, and an example for phosphate is given in Figure 33. In order to be able to compare the data, the precise measurement results of the cuvette tests were assigned to the same concentration range classes as the simple tests. Since the cuvette tests had a higher limit of quantification, the lowest three classes of the Test-Kit were combined into one class. 19 out of 23 measurements differed by a maximum of one class. Of these 19 measurements 11 were exactly the same, while in 8 samples the phosphate concentration was slightly underestimated by the Easy Life Test-Kit. No phosphate concentration above 0.5 mg/L measured by the Easy Life test was found to be lower using cuvette tests. Thus, the simple test was found to be suitable for the identification of high nutrient concentrations.

		Cuvette Test						
Classes	Range	≤ 0.075	0.075 - 0.15	0.15 - 0.35	0.35 - 0.75	0.75 - 1.25	1.25 - 1.75	> 1.75
Easy Life Test	0; 0.02; 0.05	8		2				
	0.1							
	0.2	2			4			
	0.5				2	4		
	1					1		
	1.5							
	2							

Figure 33: Validation matrix of phosphate measurements. Compared are results obtained by the Easy Life Test-Kit and Hach-Lange Cuvette Tests in concentration range classes. Concentration values in mg/L.

Volunteers registered as water rangers at KWB and carried out tests at one lake every one to two months. The aim was to find out how strong the concentration dynamics are in lakes and how important the measurement time is for the evaluation. Figure 34 shows the results for the phosphate measurement by five water rangers. A common pattern emerges that also applies to nitrite measurements. While some lakes show greater fluctuations in phosphate concentration, the concentration in other lakes remains constant at or below the test's detection limit. Lakes with high concentrations (> 0.5 mg/L) can therefore be identified with a single measurement. For Lake *Klareensee*, on the other hand, a partially elevated phosphate concentration was measured, which can only be detected through continuous measurements.

Figure 34: Dynamic of dissolved phosphate in five different Berlin Lakes.

The nitrate and ammonium tests proved insufficiently sensitive to the nutrient content of Berlin's small lakes, yielding a measured value above the detection limit only in very isolated cases.

Over the course of the project, KWB employees and students sampled as many lakes as possible to enable citywide screening. A one-time measurement can only distinguish between lakes with nutrient concentrations that are permanently below the detection limit of the tests and lakes with significantly elevated nutrient concentrations. As a result of the screening, Table 6 in Annex I lists lakes where high concentrations of phosphate (≥ 0.5 mg/L) and nitrite (≥ 0.05 mg/L) were measured. Figure 35 shows the Berlin-wide distribution of the phosphate measurements.

Figure 35: Distribution of phosphate concentration in Berlin lakes measured with test-kits.

3.1.3 IN-SITU SENSORS - OXYGEN SENSORS FOR ESTIMATING WATER QUALITY

The oxygen concentration in water depends on many factors. It is linked to trophic status via the oxygen production of algae and aquatic plants. Directly at the water surface, lakes exhibit typical oxygen dynamics with a peak in oxygen concentration during the day when sunlight stimulates oxygen production. At night, however, oxygen production ceases and respiration leads to lower oxygen concentrations. In lakes with high nutrient levels and high trophic status, the difference between minimum and maximum oxygen concentrations at the water surface is expected to be particularly large. The AD4GD project examined the extent to which oxygen concentration can be used as an indicator of the trophic status of small lakes. For this purpose, three oxygen sensors were installed at a depth of 20 cm during the summer seasons of 2024 and 2025. In total, oxygen time series of 6 lakes were recorded (Figure 36). Oxygen concentration ranges were determined in order to record oxygen dynamics. This was done weekly rather than daily and using the 10th and 90th percentiles instead of minimum and maximum values in order to disregard short-term extreme values due to weather events.

Ideally, short-term installation of the oxygen probe would allow conclusions about the water body's trophic status to be drawn. However, long-term dynamics depending on the lake's boundary conditions, such as weather, morphology, and catchment area, proved to be dominant. The smaller the lake, the more important these conditions are. As expected, it is clear that oxygen dynamics are much more pronounced in late summer than in spring in the relatively large Lietzensee. However, in the very small Ruhwaldteich, which is surrounded by trees, the lower position of the sun in late summer is assumed to prevent direct sunlight, thus influencing oxygen production. In 2025, when there was a lot of rain in Berlin in July, two lakes, *Karpfenteich* and *Breitkopfbecken*, experienced a significant drop in oxygen. Meanwhile, *Wilhelmruher See* maintained a high oxygen concentration, and fluctuations decreased. Overall, it should be noted that oxygen time series at the water surface can provide interesting insights when viewed over the long term. However, they are not suitable for drawing conclusions about the trophic status of small urban lakes through short-term use.

Figure 36: Weekly oxygen dynamic of six Berlin lakes in 2024 and 2025.

3.1.4 ESTIMATION OF THE STORMWATER INFLOW POTENTIAL

Pilot study 1 in AD4GD aims not only to identify critical situations, but also to highlight possible solutions. The CrowdWater app can be used to locate lakes with water shortages. Many of these lakes are located directly in urban areas and surrounded by sealed surfaces. If rainwater is not directed to sewage treatment plants via combined sewer systems or to larger rivers via separate sewer systems, it can be used locally as a water source for small lakes. To check this option, a generic stormwater inflow potential was developed that calculates the effective runoff volume of the surrounding areas. This is possible in Berlin because there is already a water balance model for Berlin using the ABIMO model³⁰, in which Berlin is divided into many small block areas. To calculate the potentially available water volume, all areas that are at least 50% within a distance of 200 m around the lake were included.

³⁰ <https://github.com/KWB-R/kwb.abimo>

Figure 37 shows two lakes as examples, both of which have a problem with water availability according to the CrowdWater app. The Achtrutenteich lake is mainly surrounded by green spaces. A maximum of 705 m³ of rainwater could flow into the lake from the surrounding areas in a year. In contrast, the potential at the Limonenteich lake is significantly greater at 10,695 m³. The generic approach was applied to all lakes in Berlin so that water demand and rainwater potential can be easily compared.

Figure 37: Stormwater inflow potential to two Berlin lakes. ABIMO Runoff per block area in m³ per year and m².

Rainwater runoff from urban areas, however, is always contaminated with pollutants and nutrients, which can cause problems in lakes when present in high concentrations. It is therefore essential to consider the level of pollution. In AD4GD, this consideration could not be carried out in full. Nevertheless, the groundwork was laid for intersecting the block areas of the ABIMO model with land use-specific pollutant loads, originating from the OgRe-Project (Wicke et al., 2022) dataset.

3.1.5 END-USER TOOL SPLASHBOARD

As previously outlined in Deliverable D5.1, the SplashBoard UI successfully concluded the Human-Centered Design (HCD) process and reached the final design stage, referred to as the Design Freeze. The core elements of this implementation include a main navigation header featuring tools for switching between views, a button to display a full list of water bodies, a mechanism for tagging favourite lakes for easy retrieval, and an informational button providing context about the AD4GD initiative. The main interface displays a map of Berlin along with a searchable catalogue of lakes. The map also visually represents each lake's trophic state using a color-coded **Normalized Difference Trophic Index (NDTrI)**, supported by an integrated legend (Figure 38). Moreover, a separated list of lakes is available, which can also be sorted according to this index from worst to best or vice-versa.

Figure 38: AD4GD Splashboard interface.

When users select a specific lake, they are directed to a dedicated page presenting five key widgets: one for metadata, two gauge meters displaying trophic indicators, a time series chart for observing historical lake measurements and water level forecasts, and a comment section for user contributions.

The metadata widget provides general information about the lake (such as its name, size, location, and usage) as supplied by the pilot lead. It also integrates an interactive map powered by **Geoportal Berlin**, using WMS layers via the Leaflet library. Users can navigate between these layers and legends to examine different types of geospatial data.

The trophic state and trophic trend are each displayed using their own gauge meter. These indicators give a simplified visual summary of the current ecological health and trends for each lake. Users can view this data, but no direct interaction with the meter values is available.

The statistical time series chart allows users to view historical measurements stored in **MinIO**, grouped into appropriate categories such as water level, air and water temperature, precipitation, and reference evapotranspiration. Users can tailor the graph by choosing specific timeframes and data aggregation intervals (daily, weekly, monthly, or yearly). The chart will update dynamically to match the chosen data sources and adjust the vertical axis accordingly. For instance, a selected combination might display "Water Level" in black, "Water Temperature" in green, and "Precipitation" in blue like in Figure 39.

Figure 39: AD4GD Splashboard interface (Water Level: black, Water Temperature: green, Precipitation: blue).

The prediction time series widget, on the other hand, shows forecasted lake water levels generated by AI models. These predictions correspond to varying precipitation scenarios (e.g., high, none, or average rainfall). The predicted values are shown alongside the latest actual measurements from MinIO. For example, if the user selects to view data from the past two weeks, the most recent measured water level is shown in blue, while the forecast based on a normal-precipitation scenario begins where the measurements end and is displayed in black. Users can toggle different models on and off, with the legend updating accordingly, while the axis remains fixed due to the uniform unit of measurement. Both time series charts allow users to download the graph as a PNG image or export the underlying data in CSV format.

The final widget lets authenticated users to contribute comments or observations related to a lake. If a lake has been marked as a favourite, it will appear in a user's "Favorites" section. This area offers quick access to that lake's metadata and statistics widgets and includes a direct link to the full lake detail page.

Figure 40: AD4GD SplashBoard interface (water level predictions).

3.1.6 EVALUATION / VALIDATION

This section presents the evaluation of the Splashboard UI (Pilot 1) that was developed in the context of WP6. The primary objective of this evaluation is to assess how effectively each tool addresses the user requirements (URs) that were defined during the early phases of the project and documented in D1.2. The Splashboard is designed to visualise lakes in Berlin and their water quality, with a particular focus on making environmental data more accessible to various user groups. A total of 30 user requirements were defined for this tool.

These user requirements were the result of an iterative and user-centred design process involving co-design workshops, analysis of usage context scenarios, and continuous stakeholder feedback. In earlier project phases, user needs were initially captured in the form of user stories, providing a narrative and

contextual perspective on intended use. As part of Deliverable D1.2, these stories were systematically translated into concrete and verifiable user requirements to enable a structured evaluation process. A detailed mapping between user stories and user requirements is available in D1.2 This deliverable, by contrast, focuses exclusively on assessing the implementation status of the final user requirements.

As stated in Deliverable D1.2:

"As the project approaches its final stages, the collected user requirements will play a crucial role in evaluating the completeness and effectiveness of the implementation. [...] This inspection on whether the user requirements have been considered will be outlined and detailed in Deliverable D6.2, which is due by the end of the project."

The present evaluation serves as this final verification step. It provides a systematic assessment of whether, and to what extent, the defined user requirements have been implemented in the final version of the tool. For requirements that were only partially fulfilled or not implemented at all, the evaluation includes explanations for the respective gaps. These may relate to technical limitations, prioritisation decisions, coordination challenges, or the availability of necessary data. In doing so, the evaluation not only verifies project outcomes but also highlights areas for future improvement and further development.

Evaluation Methodology

The evaluation was conducted using a structured, requirements-based inspection. This method involves systematically comparing the current implementation of the tool against a predefined set of user requirements (URs), which were documented in Deliverable 1.2. The aim was to verify whether the core functionalities and information needs identified during the design process have been effectively implemented.

Each user requirement was reviewed individually, and its implementation was assessed according to the following categories:

- Fully implemented: The requirement is completely fulfilled in the current version of the tool.
- Partially implemented: The requirement has been addressed to some extent, but relevant aspects are missing or incomplete.
- Not implemented: The requirement has not been addressed in the current version of the tool.

Requirements marked as fully implemented are considered self-explanatory and are not accompanied by additional commentary. For all partially or not implemented requirements, a brief justification is provided. These explanations refer to underlying reasons such as technical limitations, unavailable data sources, or changes in development priorities.

The assessment was carried out collaboratively by a small interdisciplinary team consisting of two usability experts and one software developer. The team jointly reviewed each requirement and inspected the respective functionality in the current prototype version. This approach follows principles of expert-based inspection techniques, as described in ISO 9241-210 (ISO 9241-210:2019), which emphasise the validation of interactive system against defined user needs and context of use.

The evaluation method can be described as a requirements-driven walkthrough, in which each tool was analysed against its formalised set of user requirements. This differs from open-ended usability testing or heuristic evaluation, as it focuses specifically on verifying whether user needs, captured and formalised as URs, have been addressed. The final set of user requirements, as defined in Deliverable D1.2, served as the evaluation framework and ensured traceability between the initial design phases and the final implementation.

Evaluation Results

The Splashboard UI, developed within the scope of Pilot 1, aims to visualise lakes located in Berlin along with their respective water quality information. In total, 30 user requirements (URs) were defined for this tool. Each requirement was individually assessed against the current state of the implementation.

Each requirement was reviewed in the context of the working prototype and categorised as fully implemented, partially implemented, not implemented, or TBD (to be determined). Requirements that were not or only partially implemented are accompanied by brief justifications. Table 2 summarises the evaluation results.

Table 2: SplashBoard requirements evaluation results.

Number	User Requirement	Inspection (Fully implemented/ Partially implemented/ Not implemented)	Comment
UR1	With the system, the user shall be able to initiate logging in to the system.	Fully implemented	
UR2	With the system, the user shall be able to enter data on a specific lake.	Partially implemented	Only administrators can perform this action due to the lack of a user role management system.
UR3	With the system, the user shall be able to access sensible data (if available for the account).	Partially implemented	The administrator can select whether the added data is visible to all users or whether they are the only one who can see it.
UR4	With the system, the user shall be able to select a lake of interest (e.g. on a map).	Fully implemented	
UR5	With the system, the user shall be able to select different locations to look for a lake.	Fully implemented	
UR6	With the system, the user shall be able to enter keywords (e.g. name of the lake) to find a specific lake.	Fully implemented	
UR7	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize a ranking of the lakes in specific area (e.g. all of Berlin, or a specific district) based on water quality.	Fully implemented	
UR8	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize the water quality index within the map.	Fully implemented	
UR9	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize the water quality of small lakes in the district.	Partially implemented	The user can recognize the water quality of small lakes in the district by marking specific lakes as favourites. District filtering is not available.
UR10	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize the water level of small lakes in the district.	Fully implemented	
UR11	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize measures of PH Value for each lake.	Not implemented	No data available.
UR12	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize measures of ammonium for each lake.	Not implemented	No data available.
UR13	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize measures of nitrogen for each lake.	Not implemented	No data available.
UR14	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize measures of zoo and phytoplankton for each lake	Not implemented	No data available.

UR15	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize measures of iron content for each lake.	Not implemented	No data available.
UR16	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize measures of water temperature for each lake.	Fully implemented	For some lakes this information is not available, but for some it is.
UR17	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize measures of depth profile for each lake.	Fully implemented	For some lakes this information is not available, but for some it is.
UR18	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize how the water quality index is calculated (Measurement period, Parameters, Calculation method, all seasons...).	Fully implemented	
UR19	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize how valid the calculated water quality index is.	Fully implemented	
UR20	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize how the data was generated/ measured.	Fully implemented	
UR21	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize when a dataset has been created (e.g. timestamp).	Fully implemented	
UR22	With the system, the user shall be able to select multiple data parameters within the same graph/diagram.	Fully implemented	
UR23	With the system, the user shall be able to change the parameters for the graph/diagram.	Fully implemented	
UR24	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize different detail levels within the diagram (e.g. days, weeks, etc.).	Fully implemented	
UR25	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize when a deviation of oxygen content in a lake has been measured.	Not implemented	No data available.
UR26	With the system, the user shall be able to initiate a download of a specific data set.	Fully implemented	
UR27	With the system, the user shall be able to initiate sharing certain datasets with other members of the system.	Partially implemented	Currently only available to the administrator.
UR28	With the system, the user shall be able to enter comments to a specific dataset.	Partially implemented	The user can enter comments to a specific lake on the lake detail page, not to a specific data set
UR29	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize who has added a comment to a specific data set.	Not implemented	It was decided that comments should not be publicly visible. Which renders this user requirement not applicable.
UR30	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize the contact information of other members of the system.	Not implemented	There are no defined user roles within the system.

Evaluation Summary and Conclusion

Out of the 30 user requirements defined for the Splashboard UI, 18 were fully implemented, 5 were partially implemented, and 7 were not implemented. An analysis of the partially and not implemented requirements reveals two main underlying causes.

The first limitation is the absence of a role and permission management system within the tool. Several user requirements could not be fulfilled because, at present, the system only distinguishes between an administrator and all other users, without a structured model for assigning user roles or defining access rights. This limitation directly affects functionalities such as entering data into the system (UR2), which is currently restricted to administrators. Similarly, the ability to share datasets with other users (UR27) is limited to administrators as well. Another example is the visibility of comments (UR29); users can leave comments, but these are only visible to the person who created them, since no public comment functionality exists. The same applies to the display of user contact information (UR30), which cannot be realised without a defined user profile structure.

The decision to restrict data upload functionality to administrators was intentional and grounded in the need to ensure the harmonisation and quality control of newly added datasets. Without harmonised data, visualisations, especially complex graphs, could easily be distorted or rendered unusable. To open this functionality to a broader group of users in the future, mechanisms would need to be put in place to ensure data quality. This could include the definition of upload templates, validation tools, or a pre-processing workflow. Additionally, a more differentiated user role model, such as data contributors, reviewers, or public users, would be required, along with clear rules regarding which types of data or comments are private, and which are visible to others.

The second group of unfulfilled user requirements concerns missing environmental data. While the technical foundation for displaying various parameters already exists within the system, the actual data sources required for certain indicators are not yet available. This concerns parameters such as pH value, ammonium, nitrogen, zoo and phytoplankton, and iron content (UR11–UR15), as well as the detection of deviations in oxygen content (UR25). Although the system would technically be capable of integrating and displaying this information, the necessary measurements have not yet been collected or made accessible. These requirements could therefore be addressed in future iterations, provided that the relevant datasets become available.

The evaluation confirms that the Splashboard UI addresses a large portion of the defined user requirements, particularly those related to data exploration, visualisation, and interpretation of lake-specific parameters. Its current implementation provides a solid basis for making environmental water data more accessible and understandable to users.

Nonetheless, some gaps remain, most notably regarding collaborative features and data granularity. These limitations stem primarily from the absence of a user role model and the unavailability of certain environmental data. Future development efforts should prioritise enhancements in user management and data integration to increase both the flexibility and the impact of the tool in real-world applications.

3.2 PILOT 2 - BIODIVERSITY

The final status of this pilot, in terms of components, integration and data pipelines, is shown in Figure 41.

Pilot 2: Biodiversity

AD4GD

Figure 41: The above diagram shows the final workflow(s) for this pilot, highlighting the use of specific components (labelled by the section where they are described) and distinguishing elements which have been reused as-is (white), extended for re-use (orange) or developed within the project (green). To clarify progress since the reporting in D6.1, bold arrows are used to distinguish workflow steps integrated between M19-M36.

3.2.1 DATA4LAND (PRE-PROCESSING)

Following the significant improvement in pre-processing, three versions of Data4Land tool have been released since reporting Deliverable D6.1 with 16 GitHub issues resolved by the development team:

- V1.0.0 (initial Notebook version)
- V1.1.1 (stable Notebook mode)
- V2.0.0 (command-line mode)

Data4Land carries out the following tasks (Figure 42):

- Preliminary analysis of input raster datasets (extraction of coordinate reference system, No Data values, bounding box, spatial resolution).
- Requests to the REST APIs, component "External Systems", to retrieve vector datasets from OpenStreetMap³¹ (OSM) and World Database on Protected Areas³² (WDPA) for LULC enrichment.

³¹ <https://www.openstreetmap.org/>

³² <https://www.protectedplanet.net/>

- Harmonisation of vector datasets: filtering values, clipping by bounding box, reprojection, translation from JSON/GeoJSON to GeoPackage format.
- Rasterisation of vector datasets; buffering; writing rasterised features to input LULC; computing 'edge effect' from biodiversity stressors.

Figure 42: Pre-processing workflow, UML component diagram.

The following inputs are used by Data4Land (Figure 43):

- land-use/land-cover (LULC) images supplied as a single input or timeseries;
- landscape impedance, based on expert knowledge, empirical data or bibliography, which represents obstacles for species to migrate between habitats, depending on the underlying land cover types;
- concordance table with mapping between LULC classes and output impedance values;
- user configuration, which includes filenames, paths, predefined queries to databases, and some ecological parameters, filled in by users, such as the character of biodiversity stressor impact.

Figure 43: Typical input and output datasets in Data4Land.

Aside from enriched land-use/land-cover image dataset(s), Data4Land also extracts biodiversity stressors based on the user configuration, and enriches the initial landscape impedance with the maximum “edge effect” from all stressors. The processed outputs may be used for subsequent analysis of habitat connectivity in Graphab, MiraMon or other software.

The main limitations met are:

- API’s performance for retrieving data for large spatial extents, such as the whole of Catalonia, might limit the processing speed (from 6.5 to 26.5 minutes, depending on the timestamp and API used).
- Ecological parameters based on expert knowledge, including landscape impedance, show high uncertainty compared to distribution models or statistical approaches (Czembor et al., 2011).
- Graphab’s high sensitivity to ecological parameters (Savary et al., 2021).

More detailed descriptions of each Data4Land blocks and limitations can be found in the readme file on GitHub.

The concise and clear description of the Data4Land functionality has also been disseminated via:

- a software paper (Kriukov et al, 2025)
- conference presentations³³
- demo at the GDDS final event³⁴
- AD4GD blogpost³⁵

³³ <https://zenodo.org/records/15237079>

³⁴ https://actiongroup.greendealdata.space/gdds_event.htm

³⁵ <https://ad4gd.eu/tool-enrich-land-use-land-cover-datasets-openstreetmap/>

3.2.2 GRAPHAB (PROCESSING AND POST-PROCESSING)

Graphab itself is a self-contained application, but a few libraries are required additionally to harmonise its outputs. Additionally, the developed workflow can be also used to access data from MinIO cloud-based data object storage (AWS-compatible).

Processing includes a few main components:

1. Java application of Graphab (v3.0.1)
2. Wrapping main Python script and underlying job, defining the commands which are relevant for local and regional connectivity studies
3. The configuration file(s), defining ecological parameters and commands scheduled to run for each case study. It is possible to save as many configuration files as user need (to run series of case studies), but they would have to specify the name of the configuration file in the beginning of the Graphab job. Once all conditions satisfied, the Graphab job can be executed through the command line: `.\graphab_job.sh`
4. Auxiliary Python scripts to harmonise processing outputs, calculate stats, visualise trends, and to access, read, and upload data from/to MinIO object storage.

All Graphab steps can be run as a single data pipeline via one command in Dockerfile: `CMD ["python3", "main.py", {case_study}, {habitat1,habitat2,habitat3}]`

For example, to run processing for all habitats in Catalonian case study, CMD should be replaced with the following:

```
CMD ["python3", "main.py", "cat_aggr_buf_390m_test", "forest,shrubland,woody,herbaceous,aquatic"]
```

Hence, the provided command-line technical solution provides users with a flexible and scalable way to evaluate habitat connectivity across multiple case studies and habitat types.

The main limitations and issues met:

- It is complicated to define all variety of visualisation tools that can be useful for the end user due to the high variability of potential input data and usage purposes (e.g., comparison between subset of indices only for the limited timeframe across different case studies).
- Initial parameterisation of Graphab software was simplified, for example, the containerised application does not include con8 option due to computation overloads.

In one of the experiments, we tested if Graphab processing and post-processing can be implemented in the external orchestration environments, such as the Kubernetes cluster managed by ATOS. We have also tested if Graphab is able to consume input data provided by different partners (Aston University and CREAM) from multiple buckets in MinIO, and upload (or update) outputs back in MinIO through S3 API wrapper.

The containerised application of Graphab with the relevant commands and post-processing scripts has been packed via Docker³⁶. Aside from the main job, this instance also includes the configuration and two volumes (Figure 44):

- Input data from MinIO buckets (land-use/land-cover, landscape impedance, CSV mapping, Graphab configurations)
- Environment file with API URL, access key and secret key for authorisation, and resources specification

³⁶ Graphab Docker: <https://hub.docker.com/r/vkrk/graphab>

The initial resources used for Graphab deployment used the minimum Java heap size of 8GB, maximum Java heap size of 16GB, and four processors. Larger resources can be used for running this proof of concept of containerised Graphab instances in future to accelerate the computation.

Figure 44: Graphab instance architecture in the Kubernetes cluster.

Additionally, the Graphab application, along with common commands to calculate habitat connectivity indices, has been implemented on Aston University’s HPC cluster, Nandi, to accelerate processing and improve performance. According to our tests, HPC configurations can speed up processing by a factor of 6.2 for calculations with low-resolution input data (390 m), and up to 26.1 for calculations with high-resolution data (30 m) (see Table 3). Even greater efficiency may be achieved, depending on the capabilities of HPC systems, input data granularity, and parameters of Graphab commands.

Table 3: Comparative performance of Graphab commands on an Ubuntu virtual machine and the Nandi HPC configurations.

Command description	Time		
	Ubuntu virtual machine, 6 CPUs	Nandi HPC, interactive job, 256 cores*	Nandi HPC, 4 GPUs
Low resolution, calculation of ecological	00:04:56	00:00:48	00:00:53

corridors (max distance = 2500 m)			
High resolution , calculation of ecological corridors (max distance = 500 m)	00:57:22	00:02:12	00:02:42
Low resolution , calculation of probability of connectivity (max distance = 2500 m)	00:02:43	00:00:39	00:00:44
High resolution , calculation of probability of connectivity (max distance = 500 m)	00:40:19	00:01:55	00:02:17

**the number of cores equals the number of nodes multiplied by the number of tasks per CPU*

3.2.3 MIRAMON PROCESSING

This subcomponent uses the MiraMon ICT (Index of Terrestrial Connectivity), a stand-alone plugin tool, which was significantly improved during months M21-26. The enhancement of the Terrestrial Connectivity algorithm is an important factor in improving the scalability of this subcomponent. The original computation of the ICT index, based on Marull J., Mallarach J.M. (2005), was performed pixel by pixel using a large number of sequential batch processing commands. This resulted in very large batch files, which were difficult to manipulate and execute (e.g., 291 Mb and 1233451 lines for an image consisting of 655 rows and 691 columns, with a spatial resolution of 390 m). These batch files were used to execute several MiraMon GIS software independent modules, or the MiraMon Support App (MSA).

A major improvement was the development of a single MiraMon MSA for ICT calculation. This stand-alone tool calculates the ICT index more efficiently without creating batch files, while also significantly reducing execution time. As an illustration, calculations for raster data with a 390m spatial resolution took approximately 7 hours using the new MSA, compared to 59.52 hours with the batch based version. It is recommended to establish a trade-off between input data granularity and workflow scalability in order to minimise computational load. If computations are required at finer resolutions and broader scales, for instance, for the whole Catalonia region at 30 m spatial resolution, the new MiraMon ICT plugin still demands substantial computational resources. As a result, ICT calculation is feasible only for two time periods: 1987 and 2022. In this case, computer vision machine learning models were used to generate ICT images. For further details, please see the Biodiversity ML sub-component (section 3.2.5) and deliverables D5.1 and D5.2.

As MiraMon applications are developed exclusively for Windows OS, implementing them on other OS was complicated by a mandatory MiraMon call to a graphical application that is not implemented by Linux. Due to this crucial limitation, this implementation has been set aside in favour of a containerised Graphab application, which provides cross-platform functionality.

Run calculations via the MiraMon graphical user interface for the single input dataset is simple, but the aim was to deliver semi-automatic processing of multiple LULC timeseries, with cleaning and harmonising input data to avoid common issues faced while running MiraMon. In this regard, the MiraMon ICT subcomponent described in four steps in the correspondent Notebook:

1. **Compression handling.** Our component, using a containerised Graphab application (or *GraphabProc*) component compresses all GeoTIFF output raster with decimal values using ZSTD compression algorithm. However, MiraMon ICT doesn't support this compression option, so input landscape impedance and affinity data are rewritten at this step. It is recommended to use one of the following algorithms instead: LZW, Deflate (zlib), TIFF-F/FX, PackBits.

2. **TIF2IMG conversion.** Input landscape impedance and affinity data in GeoTIFF format must be converted to IMG format, as MiraMon ICT natively supports only this data format. This will also create auxiliary .rel files, which are used by MiraMon to store metadata.
3. **Batch tasking.** A prepared batch file is executed to launch ICT computations. This batch file:
 - finds matching filenames of input datasets (landscape impedance and landscape affinity)
 - defines the filename of output connectivity dataset
 - defines the parameters of MiraMon ICT command.

The command uses a few parameters:

- name of a case study (text)
 - sampling distance (integer number, native MiraMon ICT parameter)
 - exploration radius (integer number, native MiraMon ICT parameter)
 - auto confirmation (boolean value, confirming if user wants to overwrite existing output datasets)
 - local directory with MiraMon ICT installation (path)
4. **IMG2TIF conversion.** Once MiraMon completes the computation, the outputs in IMG format are converted back to GeoTIFF for subsequent statistical and visual analysis.

Figure 45: An example of Miramon batch file configuration.

A few notable **limitations** exist:

1. The most common limitation is MiraMon ICT performance and time required to run this tool. For the general understanding, increasing spatial resolution leads to the proportional increase in computation time.

According to the official documentation³⁷, performance is affected not only by the spatial resolution and extent, but also by the parameters of sampling distance and exploration radius - a combination of long exploration radius and short sampling distance could take much more time.

It is simple to plan the computation resources if there is at least one elapsed time known. Elapsed time for the different sampling distance will equal to:

$$T2 = T1 \times (D2 / D1)^2$$

, where D1 - distance for calculation with known time, D2 - distance for calculation with unknown time, T1 - known time, T2 - unknown time.

2. Exploration radius, one of the MiraMon ICT parameters, can only take specific values. Exploration radius, when doubled and divided by the cell size (spatial resolution) of the original files, should be equal to an integer odd number.

Command can be invalid, depending on the parameter values, for example:

$$(525 \times 2) / 30 = 35 \text{ (valid)}$$

$$(540 \times 2) / 30 = 36 \text{ (invalid)}$$

³⁷ <https://www.miramom.cat/help/eng/msa/ICT.htm>

3. As mentioned above, MiraMon ICT doesn't support some compression algorithms of input raster datasets, such as ZSTD.

```

*****
# Main information of TIFF header file:
Columns = 1019      [*]      Rows = 745
Bits per pixel = 32
Compression = 50000 (1: Not compressed; 2-4: CCITT (fax, etc); 5: LZW;
                6: JPEG; 7: JPEG (modern); 8: Deflate (zlib);
                9-10: TIFF-F/FX; 32773: PackBits (Macintosh RLE))
Initial image offset = 3374      [*] Number of "strips" = 373
Samples by pixel = 1

ERROR:
File with compression type 50000, not supported

Press any key to continue or "Control+C" to quit... []

I C T v. 9.1f      15-04-2024 10:14
Compute the Terrestrial Connectivity Index
Xavier Pons, Nria JuliE, Ivette Serral and Joan Pino, 2021-2023 (VS,64-bit)

ERROR: semicostat_quadrat errorni
Press any key...
    
```

Figure 46: MiraMon ICT error due to unsupported compression format.

3.2.4 GBIF2IUCN (TABLE ENRICHMENT)

This tool is used to extract available data for potential sub(species) of interest from GBIF, IUCN and ancillary user-defined sources, and enrich it with spatial raster datasets in several steps (Figure 47). Registration is required to access the relevant data from some of the external services (marked 'DOPA' on the diagram, i.e. Digital Observatory for Protected Areas). These were made accessible via our collaboration with the EU's Knowledge Centre for Biodiversity based at the EU Joint Research Centre (JRC) to obtain complete data on the 2nd step.

Figure 47: Schematic workflow of GBIF2IUCN tool.

GBIF2IUCN uses and produces several datasets (Table 4), which vary in format and in their requirements status (mandatory or optional).

Table 4: Input and output datasets used in GBIF2IUCN.

Name	Description	Requirement	Format
Input			
Species list	List of scientific names of potential target sub(species)	Mandatory	CSV/XLSX
Custom conservation information	Ancillary lists for the potential target sub(species) (for example, national or regional Red Lists)	Optional	CSV/XLSX
Raster sample	Spatial raster dataset, describing (semi-) natural features of the area of interest (for example, land-use/land cover, water index, temperature regime etc.)	Optional	GeoTIFF
Output			
Enriched table	Tabular data with all data available from GBIF, IUCN and ancillary sources	Mandatory	CSV
Occurrence datacube	Occurrence datacube from GBIF fetched for filtered or all species, converted into raster dataset regridded by the input raster file (specified by user and might represent bioclimatic variables of the study area or land-use/land-cover for the further spatial analysis)	Optional	GeoTIFF

The following **steps** to enrich the list of species have been developed as Python and Shell script blocks:

1. **GBIF-enrichment** (mandatory) to fix the custom list of scientific names of species and to fetch GBIF unique keys (IDs) through GBIF Species API³⁸.
2. **IUCN-enrichment** (mandatory) using JRC's DOPA REST API services³⁹ to fetch multiple attributes of species from IUCN database and concatenate content by the unique values of IUCN IDs.
3. **GBIF-IUCN mapping** (mandatory) by scientific names from GBIF and IUCN.
4. **Additional enrichment with protection lists** from other sources (optional). For the Catalonia case study, The Red List of Spain has been used, extracting any mentions of species in the lists of rare, endangered and protected species (Listado de Especies Silvestres en Régimen de Protección Especial (LESRPE) or Categorías en el Catálogo Español de Especies Amenazadas (CEEAA)⁴⁰. This list contains unique species IDs but they do not match any known IDs in vocabularies from GBIF Backbone Taxonomy. The Red List of Catalonia accessed through Socrata API has also been used⁴¹. However, This Red List does not have any unique IDs and includes only the scientific name for identification.

³⁸ <https://techdocs.gbif.org/en/openapi/v1/species>

³⁹ <https://dopa-services.jrc.ec.europa.eu/services/>

⁴⁰ <https://www.miteco.gob.es/es/biodiversidad/temas/conservacion-de-especies/especies-proteccion-especial/ce-proteccion-listado-situacion.html>

⁴¹ <https://dev.socrata.com/foundry/analisi.transparenciacatalunya.cat/i8eg-aynu>

5. **Enrichment with GBIF datacubes** (optional). Using this block, user can access GBIF occurrence datacube⁴². Prior to execution, user should obtain the GBIF API credentials and list them in the .env file in the source repository of the database. Depending on the filters applied, requests to the GBIF database may take a long time, in some cases many minutes, to complete. Downloaded CSV file is reprojected, regridded by the input raster dataset and written to the output occurrence raster file. This optional output can be used to conduct comparative analysis between the occurrence of the target species and bio-climatic variables, land-cover types, types of habitats, verify species distribution models etc.

Detailed description of each step can be found on GitHub⁴³.

To sum up, GBIF2IUCN tool allows user to efficiently enrich the custom list of target species with the data on protection category, threats, risks, habitats and other parameters from diverse sources to address the differences in species status at global, national and regional levels. This tool has been used to choose the range of species suitable for habitat connectivity analysis in Catalonia, mainly preferring forest and shrubland habitats. As an illustration, European mink (*Mustela lutreola*), stoat (*Mustela erminea*), European badger (*Meles meles*), beech marten (*Martes foina*), common genet (*Genetta genetta*), European hedgehog (*Erinaceus europaeus*) and European wildcat (*Felis silvestris*) are mostly listed under 'Least Concern' global status defined by IUCN. However, most of these species are mentioned in the Catalonian list of protected species, and *Felis silvestris* and *Mustela erminea* are included in the Spanish List of Wild Species under Special Protection (LESRPE)⁴⁴. These differences in protection status at various scales demonstrate the importance of GBIF2IUCN tools, which allows analysing spatial variations in nature conservation.

A few GBIF2IUCN limitations should be mentioned:

- Checklistbank tools⁴⁵ do not seem stable enough to support automatic on-fly scraping of matches between GBIF and IUCN keys. Therefore, the static database derived from this tool with mapped IUCN and GBIF keys (unique IDs) for threatened species is stored separately for this workflow.
- DOPA REST services are not supporting species whose distribution data is not mapped on IUCN (for example, *Emys orbicularis*⁴⁶).
- IUCN services do not support fetching data for particular sub-species, therefore only fetching data at species level is available.
- IUCN API v4⁴⁷ has been launched and is available for non-commercial usage. However, it is not fully documented (as of 13/08/2025) and cannot be implemented in the current version of this tool.
- GBIF backbone taxonomy does not define *Reptilia* as a separate class (class with id=358 dedicated to *Reptilia* database). For the purposes of the case study, two *Reptilia* classes (*Testudines*, taxon key 11418114) and (*Squamata*, taxon key, 11592253) have been used.
- For the largest datasets (e.g. *Aves* class) we encountered memory errors which were solved by chunking and filtering out records outside of the bounding box of the input raster dataset.

3.2.5 BIODIVERSITY ML MODELS

⁴² <https://techdocs.gbif.org/en/data-use/data-cubes>

⁴³ <https://github.com/AD4GD/pilot-2-gbif-iucn>

⁴⁴ <https://www.miteco.gob.es/es/biodiversidad/temas/conservacion-de-especies/especies-proteccion-especial/ce-proteccion-listado.html>

⁴⁵ <https://www.checklistbank.org/tools/name-match-async>

⁴⁶ <https://www.iucnredlist.org/species/7717/97292665>

⁴⁷ <https://api.iucnredlist.org/api-docs/index.html>

As established in D6.1, in this subcomponent the objective was to test ML models to predict future Functional Landscape Connectivity (FLC) based on existing LULC data, training the system and verifying it by LULC and connectivity data at previous timestamps (1987-2017). This work has been fully detailed in Deliverable D5.2, but a comprehensive summary is provided below to ease readability.

As described above, the process of translating LULC maps into ICT values is computationally expensive and needs nested iterations and long calculation times, since for each pixel in the LULC map, a calculation has to be done in its neighbourhood to compute the ICT value. The idea, hence, is to use AI to replace this exact calculation by the approximation provided by the inference of an AI model to try to achieve satisfactory results in a considerably less amount of time. The impact of having this kind of analysis is crucial for actions such as evaluating the implications of introducing a modification in the landscape (e.g., building a highway dissecting a forest habitat). In that scenario, many different possible scenarios would have to be evaluated, and the time consumed to evaluate all of them would make this feasibility study not viable.

Regarding model development, the task of mapping LULC data to connectivity maps falls under the domain of image-to-image translation. The first models considered were models commonly used in the field of spatial prediction, such as Fully Convolutional Networks (FCNs) and simpler architectures like U-Net. However, these models were discarded due to their limitations in handling the complex spatial dependencies present in the connectivity maps. Pix2Pix offers a significant advantage by producing not only accurate but also visually coherent outputs, which is crucial for environmental applications where realistic image representation plays a significant role in decision-making.

The Pix2Pix model, based on Conditional Generative Adversarial Networks (cGANs), excels in tasks where the goal is to generate high-quality, realistic images conditioned on an input image. In this case, the model is conditioned on LULC maps to generate connectivity maps. Pix2Pix works by utilizing two main components: the generator and the discriminator. The generator creates the connectivity map from the LULC map, while the discriminator evaluates whether the generated map is realistic enough to be classified as "real" or "fake." Through adversarial training, where the generator learns to deceive the discriminator into thinking its generated maps are real, the generator improves over time, becoming better at producing high-quality outputs. This approach is particularly beneficial when the spatial relationships and fine details in the connectivity map are crucial, as it ensures the generated map captures complex ecological patterns.

Regarding the datasets used for training and validation, LULC maps representing five relevant connectivity indexes have been used: forest, herbaceous crops, woody crops, shrublands and aquatic environment, so a model had to be trained for each of these maps. For each of these LULC maps, two variations with the same spatial extent have been used for ML model:

- High-resolution LULC maps: 8651x8981 pixels, resulting in a 30 m spatial resolution
- Low-resolution LULC maps: 655x690 pixels, resulting in a 390 m spatial resolution.

This difference in the resolution of the input dataset has a direct impact in the ML model architecture: the ML models used to process images perform some operations (mainly, convolutions and deconvolutions) that have the objective of reducing and increasing the image size. Consequently, the size of the input image has a direct impact in the number of operations that must be performed. Hence, two variations of the ML models have been built, one for the high-resolution images, and another for the low-resolution ones. This makes a total of 10 models that have been trained in the context of WP5 to test the hypothesis established for pilot 2.

As described in D5.2, in order to get a more manageable ML model, the input images have been sliced, transforming the input images to slices of 256x156 for the high-resolution scenario, and of 32x32 in the low-resolution one. Consequently, the model generates predictions for the slices, so a postprocessing step is needed once the inference has finished. This post-processing consists of reconstructing the output

image by stitching back together the different slices. To do so, a Hanning window is applied to reduce edge artifacts and smooth transitions between slices, improving the final image quality. This smoothing effect helps preserve fine details and coherence in the reconstructed image, which is crucial for tasks like connectivity mapping.

Consequently, this component is further divided into three main subcomponents: preprocessing, model training and inference, and post-processing. These building blocks have been implemented and deployed in a pipeline that works on demand, following the ML lifecycle presented in D5.1 and running onto the HPC resources of AD4GD. Hence, the AI prediction pipeline for pilot 2 works as follows:

- First, the incoming raw data is stored in MiniIO, creating a large historical dataset used to develop, train and test the pilot's models.
- The model is exposed through a REST API to be called by the end-user in an on-demand fashion.
- To perform these API calls, the end user needs to provide an input image. When this is performed, the first action is to preprocess the input image to slice it as described above.
- When the model finishes the inference, the post-processing step is executed, providing an output image with the results to the frontend of the system, which formats and presents the result to the end-user. The frontend implementation will be detailed in Section 3.2.6.

Figure 48 represents this process. It should be noted that the REST API to generate predicted maps is seamlessly integrated with the frontend developed in the context of T5.5.

Finally, regarding the results obtained with the AI models trained for pilot 2, D5.2 provides an in-depth study of both the accuracy of the models and the time taken for the models to generate a predicted map, and these values have been compared to those obtained with the MiraMon software (that are considered the ground truth). Regarding accuracy, the obtained results show promising results for the Forest Connectivity Index, but inconclusive results are obtained for the rest of the models due to the training dataset being not sufficiently large. However, the Forest scenario demonstrates that, given a sufficiently large training dataset, an AI-based tool can indeed be a viable alternative to the MiraMon software, since the obtained results are sufficiently good and the timeframe for generating one ICT map has been drastically reduced (going from weeks to minutes).

Figure 48: Pilot 2 "on demand" ML Model's inferencing schema (extracted from D5.2).

3.2.6 END-USER TOOL BIOCONN

In contrast to SplashBoard, the development of the BioConnect interface began later, following the completion of the Human-Centered Design (HCD) process and the Design Freeze. Feedback from interviews with potential end users and the pilot lead partner informed the final design. The tool features a

centralized home page with an interactive map that enables users to explore various layers related to land use, bioconnectivity indexes, species distributions, infrastructure, and historical datasets focused on the Catalonia region.

Figure 49: AD4GD BioConn interface.

A prominent functionality of BioConnect is the ability for users to create scenarios by simulating changes in land use. The interface allows users to draw a polygon on the map to represent an area of change. Instructions for using this tool are provided via an on-screen help box. Once a polygon is defined, the user can assign it a new land-use classification—for instance, “Forestland” (shown in green with the value 6). A drop-down menu and a corresponding legend provide the full list of categories: “Aquatic”, “Built area”, “Herbaceous cropland”, “Woody cropland”, “Shrubland and grassland”, “Forestland”, and “Bare/sparse vegetation”.

Figure 50: AD4GD BioConn interface (recalculation of connectivity index).

Users can choose to recalculate a bioconnectivity index for the modified area by selecting either high- or low-resolution processing. The available index types—such as those for “Aquatic”, “Herbaceous cropland”, “Woody cropland”, “Shrubland and grassland”, or “Forestland”—are selectable based on API availability. Currently, high-resolution recalculations are only supported for Forestland. The tool validates the selected combinations to prevent unsupported configurations from being submitted. By clicking “Process Scenario”, the user sends an API request to the ATOS backend with the specified parameters. Additionally, users have the option to download the newly created scenario as GeoTiff for external tool usage or save it for later use. The saved scenario will be stored separately and can be accessed via the “Saved scenario” tab on the header. Users can preview all their saved scenarios, download/upload them as JSON and even process them the same way as before. Once processed, the results are shown in a comparative view.

Figure 51: AD4GD BioConn interface (saved scenarios).

The comparison screen displays the recalculated bioconnectivity map (on the right) alongside the original version (on the left). Users can explore these interactive maps to assess the changes resulting from their scenario. A red dotted square highlights the recalculated area to assist with orientation. The same species and infrastructure layers are also available for further analytical usage.

Figure 52: AD4GD BioConn interface (scenario comparisons).

3.2.6.1 EVALUATION / VALIDATION

The following section presents the evaluation of the BioConnect tool, developed in the context of Pilot 2 within Work Package 6 (WP6). As in the case of Pilot 1, this evaluation focuses on verifying the extent to which the final implementation meets the previously defined user requirements (URs). The BioConnect tool is intended to support stakeholders in visualising ecological connectivity in the Barcelona region, with a particular emphasis on land use scenarios and biodiversity planning. In total, 49 user requirements were formulated for this tool.

These requirements were defined as part of the same co-design and analysis process described in the context of the Splashboard UI. Building on user stories developed during early design phases, the project team consolidated these into concrete and verifiable user requirements documented in Deliverable 1.2. For a detailed mapping between user stories and the final URs, as well as insights into the underlying rationale, Deliverable 1.2 serves as the main reference. This section focuses solely on evaluating the level of implementation of the defined requirements.

As described earlier in this document, this evaluation forms the final verification step outlined in Deliverable D1.2. It assesses which user requirements were fully addressed, which were only partially realised, and which were not implemented. When requirements were not fully met, potential reasons are briefly discussed, including technical constraints, development scope limitations, or availability of required data.

Evaluation Methodology

The evaluation approach applied to the BioConnect tool mirrors the methodology used for Pilot 1. A structured, requirements-based walkthrough was conducted to compare the final implementation of the tool against the user requirements defined in Deliverable D1.2.

Each user requirement was reviewed individually and classified into one of three categories:

- Fully implemented: The requirement is fully realised in the current version.
- Partially implemented: The requirement has been addressed in part, but not comprehensively.

- Not implemented: The requirement has not been addressed at all.

As before, only partially or not implemented requirements are accompanied by commentary that explains the reasons for any shortcomings. These include technical limitations, unresolved dependencies, or data-related issues. The evaluation was carried out collaboratively by the same interdisciplinary team that reviewed Pilot 1, consisting of two usability experts and one developer.

The evaluation again draws on principles of expert-based inspection, particularly as outlined in ISO 9241-210 (ISO 9241-210:2019). The method prioritises alignment with user needs, as captured in the formalised set of user requirements. Unlike usability testing, which focuses on user behaviour, this approach verifies whether intended functionalities were implemented as planned. The consistency in methodology ensures comparability between both pilot evaluations.

Evaluation Results

The BioConnect tool, developed within the scope of Pilot 2, aims to visualise bioconnectivity data in the region of Barcelona. The objective is to support the identification of ecological corridors, fragmentation zones, and overall landscape connectivity based on various environmental and spatial indicators.

A total of 49 user requirements (URs) were defined for this pilot during the early design phases and consolidated in Deliverable D1.2. These requirements reflect the functional and informational needs of stakeholders involved in biodiversity monitoring, land planning, and environmental protection.

The evaluation was conducted collaboratively by two usability experts and one software developer. Each user requirement was examined against the current implementation of the BioConnect prototype and categorised as fully implemented, partially implemented, not implemented, or TBD (to be determined). For requirements that were not or only partially implemented, justifications are provided.

Table 5: BioConn requirements evaluation results.

Number	User Requirement	Inspection (Fully implemented/ Partially implemented/ Not implemented)	Comment
UR1	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize what the "BioConnect Tool" is about.	Fully implemented	
UR2	With the system, the user shall be able to initiate the "BioConnect Tool".	Fully implemented	
UR3	With the system, the user shall be able to select specific species to show their connectivity on the map.	Not implemented	Connectivity cannot be calculated for a specific species. However, the occurrence of a specific species can be displayed as a separate layer.
UR4	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize the type of data that is available.	Fully implemented	
UR5	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize how the shown connectivity map is calculated.	Fully implemented	
UR6	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize how trustworthy (or uncertain) the calculation of connectivity is.	Not implemented	Information is missing
UR7	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize at which spatial resolution the map is calculated.	Fully implemented	
UR8	With the system, the user shall be able to select forest as a type of land use for	Fully implemented	

	connectivity calculations.		
UR9	With the system, the user shall be able to select shrubland as a type of land use for connectivity calculations.	Fully implemented	
UR10	With the system, the user shall be able to select herbaceous crops as a type of land use for connectivity calculations.	Fully implemented	
UR11	With the system, the user shall be able to select woody crops as a type of land use for connectivity calculations.	Fully implemented	
UR12	With the system, the user shall be able to select aquatic as a type of land use for connectivity calculations.	Fully implemented	
UR13	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize which filters are affecting the connectivity map.	Fully implemented	
UR14	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize which filters are only layers on top of the connectivity map.	Fully implemented	
UR15	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize when a layer was last updated.	Not implemented	Information is missing
UR16	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize from what year the information of a layer is.	Not implemented	Information is missing
UR17	With the system, the user shall be able to select a layer showing the cadastral information of the area.	Fully implemented	
UR18	With the system, the user shall be able to select a geometry file with geolocation data to find out what effect certain constructions in specific areas would have on animal connectivity.	Not implemented	Not technically feasible with the current system infrastructure. Uploading user-defined geometry files is not compatible with the current system due to the potentially large and complex nature of such files. There is no reliable way to validate file format or data quality. Unlike the drawing tool, which allows us to guide users toward small, manageable areas, uploaded files may exceed processing limits and conflict with the current logic for assigning values to polygons.
UR19	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize instruction on how to upload a file (e.g. what format is required).	Not implemented	This requirement depends on the implementation of UR18, which has not been realised.
UR20	With the system, the user shall be able to enter a land use change scenario to see its impact on connectivity.	Fully implemented	
UR21	With the system, the user shall be able to change the setting on whether to see the coordinates on the map.	Not implemented	This functionality was originally omitted during development but may be reconsidered for future

			iterations.
UR22	With the system, the user shall be able to enter road as a land use change.	Not implemented	Not technically feasible with the current system infrastructure.
UR23	With the system, the user shall be able to enter urban area as a land use change.	Fully implemented	Urban area is described as build area within tool
UR24	With the system, the user shall be able to enter industrial area as a land use change.	Fully implemented	Industrial area is described as build area within tool
UR25	With the system, the user shall be able to enter channels as a land use change.	Not implemented	Not technically feasible with the current system infrastructure.
UR26	With the system, the user shall be able to enter railroads as a land use change.	Not implemented	Not technically feasible with the current system infrastructure.
UR27	With the system, the user shall be able to enter wildlife crossing as a land use change.	Not implemented	Not technically feasible with the current system infrastructure.
UR28	With the system, the user shall be able to enter habitat restoration as a land use change.	Not implemented	Not technically feasible with the current system infrastructure.
UR29	With the system, the user shall be able to enter forest as a land use change.	Fully implemented	
UR30	With the system, the user shall be able to enter crops as a land use change.	Fully implemented	Crops refers to woody or herbaceous crops (see UR32 and UR33)
UR31	With the system, the user shall be able to enter shrublands as a land use change.	Fully implemented	
UR32	With the system, the user shall be able to enter woody crops as a land use change.	Fully implemented	
UR33	With the system, the user shall be able to enter herbaceous crops as a land use change.	Fully implemented	
UR34	With the system, the user shall be able to enter aquatic as a land use change.	Fully implemented	
UR35	With the system, the user shall be able to enter a specific area for a land use change.	Fully implemented	
UR36	With the system, the user shall be able to change the position of the set pins when creating a new scenario.	Fully implemented	
UR37	With the system, the user shall be able to enter an area for land use change by entering different coordinates.	Not implemented	Depends on UR21, which has not been realised.
UR38	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize the cadastral information when selecting an area for land use change.	Not implemented	Technical possible but no time for development
UR39	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize the connectivity in a scenario over time to also see the future impact.	Partially implemented	No data available for future projection, only status quo
UR40	With the system, the user shall be able to select multiple scenarios in order to compare them.	Not implemented	Not technically feasible with the current system infrastructure.
UR41	With the system, the user shall be able to change the parameters of the created	Fully implemented	

	scenario to be able to view different land uses.		
UR42	With the system, the user shall be able to create a scenario (map).	Fully implemented	
UR43	With the system, the user shall be able to name a scenario (map).	Fully implemented	
UR44	With the system, the user shall be able to change the name of a scenario (map).	Fully implemented	
UR45	With the system, the user shall be able to share a scenario (map).	Fully implemented	
UR46	With the system, the user shall be able to enter text comments in a certain area of a scenario (map).	Not implemented	This feature could not be implemented due to time constraints during development.
UR47	With the system, the user shall be able to initiate an export of a created scenario (map) to a local file system.	Fully implemented	
UR48	With the system, the user shall be able to recognize all scenarios that were created.	Fully implemented	
UR49	With the system, the user shall be able to delete scenarios that were created.	Fully implemented	

Evaluation Summary and Conclusions

Out of the 49 user requirements defined for the BioConnect tool, 31 were fully implemented, 2 were partially implemented, and 15 were not implemented. The analysis of the partially and not implemented requirements reveals several recurring causes that can be grouped into three main categories.

The first group consists of requirements that could not be fulfilled due to missing or unavailable data. While the system infrastructure would support the display of additional contextual information (e.g. metadata or timestamps), such information was not available at the time of development. This applies to requirements like UR6 (uncertainty of connectivity calculation), UR15 (last update of a layer), and UR16 (data year of a layer). In these cases, it was not a technical limitation that prevented implementation, but rather the absence of corresponding data sources.

The second group of non- or only partially implemented requirements concerns limitations in data processing and infrastructure. Several requirements involve user-defined inputs (e.g. uploading geometry files, entering coordinates, comparing scenarios) that are not feasible with the current technical setup. For example, uploading external geometry files (UR18) is not supported due to the complexity and size of potential inputs, which could conflict with system logic and exceed processing capabilities. Similarly, UR21 and UR37 through UR40 were not implemented. These include functionalities such as displaying map coordinates, defining areas through coordinate input, comparing multiple scenarios, or calculating connectivity impacts over time. While these are all conceptually relevant, their implementation would have required additional architectural components or extensive backend logic, which could not be prioritised within the project's development timeframe. In the case of UR21, for example, the coordinate functionality was initially deprioritised under the assumption that area definition would be handled via file uploads, an assumption that became outdated once it was clear that uploading was not feasible. Additionally, UR46, which concerns the ability to add comments to a scenario map, was not realised due to time constraints, even though it is not technically impossible.

A third group of unmet requirements concerns land use change types that are not supported in the current version of the tool due to technical limitations. This includes requirements such as UR22, which requests the integration of "road" as a land use type, and UR25 to UR28, which refer to other change types such as channels, railroads, wildlife crossings, and habitat restoration. In all these cases, the core issue lies in the complexity of integrating these specific land use types into the existing connectivity model. Doing so would require structural adjustments to the model logic, input data handling, and potentially also

visualisation strategies. These features were therefore not included at this stage but may be considered for future iterations of the tool if the technical and conceptual foundations allow for their integration.

The evaluation of the BioConnect tool demonstrates that a substantial portion of the user requirements, particularly those related to scenario creation, land use classification, and map interaction, were successfully implemented. These functionalities provide a solid foundation for supporting key use cases in biodiversity monitoring and landscape planning.

At the same time, the evaluation reveals a number of technical and infrastructural limitations that prevented the realisation of more advanced features. Requirements involving the integration of complex land use change types, user-defined geometry uploads, and coordinate-based inputs could not be addressed within the scope of the current prototype. In many cases, these were not conceptually unfeasible, but rather constrained by development capacity, architectural limitations, or the need for further refinement of the connectivity model. Moreover, the absence of certain contextual data, such as timestamps or metadata, also limited the implementation of information-related requirements.

It should also be noted that the development of BioConnect was affected by external coordination challenges. In particular, scheduling and conducting early evaluation sessions with end users proved more difficult than expected. As a result, the identification of user requirements for Pilot 2 was delayed compared to Pilot 1. This left less time for implementation and integration of requested features. Some functionalities that are currently missing may therefore not be excluded for technical reasons but rather due to time constraints within the project timeline.

Despite these gaps, the current version of the tool represents a meaningful step toward enabling more data-informed planning for ecological connectivity. The modular structure of BioConnect allows for future extensions, and many of the non-implemented requirements can potentially be revisited in subsequent development phases, provided that technical and organisational conditions permit.

Overall, the evaluation confirms that BioConnect succeeds in delivering core functionalities aligned with the project's objectives. It offers an initial, functional framework that can be expanded and refined through further iterations, guided by the detailed insights derived from this requirement-based evaluation.

3.3 PILOT 3 – AIR QUALITY

The final status of this pilot, in terms of components, integration and data pipelines, is shown in Figure 53.

Figure 53: The above diagram shows the final workflow(s) for this pilot, highlighting the use of specific components (labelled by the section where they are described) and distinguishing elements which have been reused as-is (white), extended for re-use (orange) or developed within the project (green). To clarify progress since the reporting in D6.1, bold arrows are used to distinguish workflow steps integrated between M19-M36.

3.3.1 TRUSTWORTHINESS ASSESSMENT AND HARMONISATION

The data processing and harmonisation pipeline in Pilot 3 transforms raw, unevenly distributed time series from low-cost IoT air quality sensors into consistent, high-resolution spatiotemporal datasets. This pipeline is essential to ensure that the observational data are trustworthy, scientifically usable, and compatible with downstream workflows such as model validation or exposure mapping, and to facilitate the integration into further application (such as the ECWMF’s Cross Data Store⁴⁸).

The pipeline consists of two tightly coupled stages:

1. Trustworthiness assessment and correction, where unreliable or biased data are identified and corrected, and
2. Spatial harmonisation, where the cleaned time series are interpolated into gridded 3D data cubes using kriging techniques.

⁴⁸ <https://xds-dev.ecmwf.int/datasets/derived-air-quality>

Both stages are built to be modular and scalable, capable of handling large volumes of heterogeneous observations across multiple years and sensor network configurations.

Trustworthiness Filtering and Correction

Low-cost sensor data are often affected by systematic biases, environmental sensitivities such as relative humidity, and inconsistencies across hardware models or installation practices. To address these issues, the Trustworthiness Framework in Pilot 3 implements a multi-step quality control and correction process that combines rule-based filtering with machine learning.

The process begins with plausibility checks, where physically implausible values, such as negative PM concentrations or sensors producing constant readings over extended periods, are flagged and removed. In addition, a median filter is applied to the hourly time series to smooth high-frequency noise, providing an initial stage of harmonisation and stability.

Next follows a data-driven outlier filtering step. Each IoT measurement is compared with CAMS Europe air quality forecasts at a spatial resolution of 0.1 degrees. For every time step and station, the ratio α equals IoT divided by CAMS is calculated. The natural logarithm of this ratio is then aggregated within several spatial radii, and interquartile statistics are used to define whisker thresholds. Measurements that fall outside these thresholds are identified as statistical outliers and excluded from further processing.

To account for spatial heterogeneity in sensor distribution and behaviour, the remaining stations are grouped into clusters using the OPTICS clustering algorithm. These clusters represent dense, spatially coherent sensor groupings and serve as the basis for localized correction and interpolation in later stages.

The central element of the correction framework is a supervised machine learning model based on the XGBoost algorithm. The model takes as input the raw PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ values from Sensor.Community, meteorological parameters from ERA5 such as two-meter temperature, relative humidity, and boundary layer height, as well as trigonometric representations of the day of year and a cluster identifier. It is trained on data from 2017 to 2021, validated in 2022, and tested on independent 2023 observations. The model performs well, achieving an R^2 of approximately 0.89. It captures key physical effects including seasonal variability in aerosol sources and particle growth associated with humidity.

For sensors not assigned to any cluster, predictions are computed using an inverse-distance weighted ensemble of the available cluster models. This ensures that the correction procedure is applicable across the entire domain, even in regions with limited reference data.

The outcome is a harmonised and bias-corrected collection of IoT time series, which can then be used as input for spatial interpolation. Further methodological details, supporting figures, and diagnostics are available in Deliverable D4.3.

Spatial Harmonisation and Data Cube Generation

Once the IoT sensor data have been filtered and bias-corrected, they are transformed into structured geospatial products through kriging-based spatial interpolation. This step enables the construction of harmonised data cubes with consistent spatial and temporal resolution, where all output fields are gridded on a uniform lattice with a resolution of 0.01° in both latitude and longitude, approximately equivalent to 1 km.

The interpolation relies on a kriging-based observation operator inspired by techniques used in data assimilation. This operator converts irregularly spaced point measurements into continuous spatial fields, ensuring compatibility with model-based workflows and geospatial analyses. To stabilize variance and

improve statistical robustness, all interpolation is performed on log-transformed PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ concentrations.

Two complementary kriging strategies are employed to generate the final gridded products:

- **Penalized Ordinary Kriging (IoT-only product):** This method is applied across the full European domain and uses only the corrected IoT sensor observations. A penalization term is introduced to mitigate overfitting in areas with sparse sensor coverage. The result is a smooth, high-resolution field that generalises well even in data-limited regions.
- **Universal Kriging with External Drift (IoT+CAMS product):** In regions with denser sensor networks, such as Central Europe, the interpolation is enhanced by including CAMS Europe air quality analysis fields as an auxiliary variable. This external drift component allows the interpolation to capture both the fine-scale spatial patterns observed by the sensors and the broader, physically consistent structures represented in the CAMS model data.

To retain urban-scale features and represent fine spatial heterogeneity more accurately, interpolation is also applied within spatial clusters identified by the OPTICS algorithm. These clusters define locally coherent sensor groups and enable a second, more localized kriging pass, which helps maintain intra-urban detail that would otherwise be smoothed out by a global fit.

All resulting data cubes are produced at both hourly and daily resolution and cover the full Pilot 3 time range from 2018 to 2024. The interpolation algorithms are implemented in PyTorch, allowing for GPU acceleration and enabling efficient, high-throughput processing suitable for retrospective analysis and near-real-time applications alike.

3.3.2 COLLOCATION AND QUALITY-CHECKING OF LOW-COST SENSORS

The ingestion tool described in Section 2.1 has allowed us to ingest and harmonise data from sensor types not available through other aggregation platforms (e.g. mobile personal devices), and has also facilitated the easy intercomparison of data from experimentally collocated sensors, to evaluate quality and consistency (Figure 54). The semantic enrichment which has been incorporated in the second half of the project improves the opportunity to identify data which is genuinely comparable and highlight the need for additional correction steps before data are combined (e.g. avoiding the direct comparison of humidity-corrected particulate data from a PurpleAir instrument with raw particulate data from a Sensor.Community AirRohr).

Figure 54: Intercomparison of pairs of collocated sensors, showing non-systematic discrepancies (left) and systematic bias (right)

An example notebook can be found at <https://github.com/AD4GD/Component-AirQualityDataIngestion/blob/main/analysis/>, which:

- Queries the API with a bounding box to retrieve all sensors located within a specific area
- Identifies the consistent observable properties between sensor platform types
- Plots time series of those observable properties to visualise consistency (see Figure 55).

Figure 55: A graph showing PM2.5 readings from a range of collocated sensor platform types (anonymised for this publication).

The resulting estimates of data quality can be documented using the ISO metadata standard with DQ_QualityReport elements and published in Geonetwork (Section 2.9). The ingestion / collocation tool has not currently been integrated into the ECMWF analysis described above (Section 3.3.1), but is available for future re-use and integration.

3.3.3 END-USER TOOL

In pilot 3, there were no user requirements collected through the Human Centered Design process. In here a more traditional approach on the analysis of the usefulness of the data generated is presented.

All processed data products from Pilot 3 are made accessible via ECMWF's Cross Data Store (XDS)⁴⁹. The XDS is a federated data access infrastructure that enables users to discover, query, and retrieve environmental datasets from multiple thematic sources through a unified interface.

Both the IoT-only and IoT+CAMS gridded data cubes, along with accompanying metadata, are published in standardized formats and registered within the XDS. This ensures compliance with FAIR principles and supports integration with other Copernicus data products and services, such as those provided by CAMS and C3S.

Through the XDS, researchers, public agencies, and application developers can seamlessly access harmonised air quality data in combination with complementary geospatial datasets, facilitating cross-domain environmental analysis and decision support.

3.3.4 SCIENTIFIC EVALUATION / VALIDATION

⁴⁹ <https://xds-dev.ecmwf.int/datasets/derived-air-quality>

The scientific validation of the Pilot 3 data products is based on a detailed comparison between the gridded fields and independent reference observations from EEA air quality monitoring stations across Europe. To isolate the contribution and added value of the IoT data, the evaluation focuses specifically on the IoT-only dataset. Key aspects under review include spatial consistency, bias reduction, and the ability to reproduce established patterns in air pollution variability.

The quantitative assessment relies on standard statistical metrics to evaluate the agreement between the interpolated IoT data and co-located reference measurements. Specifically, we compute the mean bias, the root mean square error (RMSE), and the mean normalized bias (MNB), defined as follows:

$$\text{Bias} = \text{mean}(\text{IoT} - \text{EEA})$$

$$\text{RMSE} = \sqrt{\text{mean}((\text{IoT} - \text{EEA})^2)}$$

$$\text{MNB} = \text{sum}(\text{IoT} - \text{EEA}) / \text{sum}(\text{EEA})$$

Figure 56 and Figure 57 show maps of these metrics. The results indicate a high level of agreement between the interpolated IoT-only fields and the EEA reference observations. The best performance is observed in Central Europe, where the density of low-cost sensors is highest.

Figure 56: Skill scores of intercomparison between daily-averaged, gridded IoT-only product and EEA reference stations for PM2.5.. Left: Bias; center: RMSE; right: mean normalized bias.

Figure 57: Skill scores of intercomparison between daily-averaged, gridded IoT-only product and EEA reference stations for PM10.. Left: Bias; center: RMSE; right: mean normalized bias.

For further analysis, the MNB is computed separately by station type (background, industrial, traffic) and area classification (urban, suburban, and rural). The results, summarized in histograms, reveal that for

PM2.5 the IoT-only product performs comparably to the CAMS Europe analysis. For PM10, it even outperforms CAMS, particularly in urban areas. This is a noteworthy finding, especially considering that many EEA reference stations are assimilated into the CAMS Europe modelling system. In rural and suburban regions, the IoT-only results are somewhat less accurate. However, the lower sensor density in these areas likely contributes to increased uncertainty and reduced representativeness in the skill scores.

Figure 58: Histograms of mean normalized bias between daily-averaged gridded IoT-only product and EEA reference stations as well as CAMS Europe analysis and EEA reference stations for PM2.5. Separation into station type according to categorization of EEA.

Figure 59: Histograms of mean normalized bias between daily-averaged gridded IoT-only product and EEA reference stations as well as CAMS Europe analysis and EEA reference stations for PM10. Separation into area type according to categorization of EEA.

Use Case Relevance

The validated gridded products produced in Pilot 3 support a range of scientifically and societally relevant applications. Their dense spatial coverage and high temporal resolution make them well-suited for the evaluation of regional and urban-scale air quality models, offering an independent observational layer against which model output can be compared.

The fine spatial resolution enables detailed identification of air pollution hotspots, including locations that are not covered by regulatory monitoring networks (Figure 60). This can support urban planning, traffic management, and targeted mitigation strategies. In addition, the harmonised datasets provide a robust basis for public health applications. They can be used in exposure assessment and health impact modelling, such as estimating excess mortality or morbidity linked to air pollution at the city or neighbourhood scale (Figure 61).

Figure 60: PM2.5 exceedance days for Sofia from CAMS Europe (left) and IoT+CAMS (right) for 2022.

Figure 61: Left panel shows the population attribution function (PAF) from IoT+CAMS. The center panel shows excess mortality estimated from CAMS Europe, and the right panel shows excess mortality derived from IoT+CAMS data (all for 2022).

Overall, the results demonstrate that when properly quality-checked and regridded, data from low-cost IoT sensors can serve as a scientifically robust and operationally useful source of high-resolution air quality information. The products developed in Pilot 3 offer a valuable complement to traditional air quality monitoring and forecasting systems, filling gaps in spatial and temporal coverage.

As a concrete example of use beyond the regulatory monitoring domain, Figure 62 and Figure 63 depict how the IoT-only product has been applied in the Greater Moscow area. For better data inspection, Figure 63 provides a 15-day running mean of the same PM concentrations. In this region, no official reference observations are available, highlighting the potential of citizen-sourced sensor data to extend air quality monitoring into otherwise unobserved areas. In the case of PM2.5, CAMS Europe and IoT only agree well over the whole time period. In contrast, the PM10 values from CAMS Europe indicate a systematic low bias with respect to the IoTonly product, which is in line with the findings from the intercomparisons to EEA reference stations (Figure 59).

Figure 62: Time series of hourly PM2.5 (top) and PM10 (bottom) for Greater Moscow Area derived from corrected IoT air quality measurements and CAMS Europe model data from January 2019 to December 2024.

Figure 63: Time series of running 15-day average from hourly PM10 for Greater Moscow Area derived from corrected IoT air quality measurements and CAMS Europe model data from January 2019 to December 2024.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The Green Deal Data Space should be implemented as a set of interoperable building blocks (i.e. components) which will be required for tackling interdisciplinary challenges of the European Green Deal. AD4GD demonstrated the capability to combine some of the components to implement 3 pilots in 3 thematic areas of the European Green Deal: water quantity and quality, terrestrial biodiversity connectivity and air quality.

Pilot 1 (Water) is related to urban lakes in Berlin, where we specifically focussed on water availability and quality, which particularly affect provisioning and recreation ecosystem services. In this pilot, satellite data and volunteered CitSci measurements are used to enrich a Dataspace which is currently dominated by IoT sources such as *in-situ* sensors for water level, conductivity, oxygen etc. A Water Quality Index representing trophic state (NDTrI) and a Water Availability Index (WAI) are computed and a Machine Learning model can be used to predict the status of Berlin lakes in 3 scenarios: no precipitation, some precipitation and abundant precipitation. While citizens cannot provide precise measurements, they can provide valuable information to compare and classify lakes and set priorities on where an mitigation action is needed more urgently. This means that citizen science can help in the decision making process. Analysis of the non-fulfilled requirements in the user interface reveals that pH, ammonium, nitrogen, zoo- and phyto-plankton, and iron content, as well as the detection of deviations in oxygen content are not available because the necessary measurements have not yet been collected or made accessible. There is a need to capture far more data in the GDDS. However, an evaluation confirms that the pilot 1 addresses a large portion of the user requirements, particularly those related to data exploration, visualisation, and interpretation of lake-specific parameters.

Pilot 2: (Biodiversity) identified key locations for landscape functional connectivity and endangered species persistence by explicitly combining and cross-validating the results from different accepted modelling approaches, based on time series of land-use / land-cover (LULC) maps. Several data sources such as IoT, CitSci and remote sensing were used. Biodiversity connectivity is a good indicator for decision making allowing policy makers and land managers to understand the impact of some land cover change in the terrestrial ecosystems. However the current methods to compute connectivity are cumbersome and very slow. An alternative development using ML was possible but had some limitations due to restricted training sets. This and other constraints resulted in technical and infrastructural limitations that prevented the realisation of more advanced features that users demanded. Requirements involving the integration of complex land use change types, adding user-defined geometry modifications in land cover and coordinate-based operations were not possible to implement in the AD4GD timeframe.

Pilot 3 (Air quality and pollution) is a context where the use of Earth Observation (EO) data through their generation of the authoritative CAMS air quality maps and forecasts. We demonstrated the potential of IoT data and CitSci observations to spatially enrich air quality CAMS products. The results indicate a high level of agreement between the interpolated IoT-only fields and the EEA reference observations. The best performance is observed in Central Europe, where the density of low-cost sensors is highest. The results reveal that for PM_{2.5} the IoT-only product performs comparably to the CAMS Europe analysis. For PM₁₀, it even outperforms CAMS, particularly in urban areas. In rural and suburban regions, the IoT-only results are somewhat less accurate. However, the lower sensor density in these areas probably contributes to increased uncertainty and reduced representativeness of the IoT stations. In urban areas, the dense spatial coverage and high temporal resolution make IoT measurements well-suited for the evaluation of regional and urban-scale air quality models, offering an independent observational layer against which model output can be compared. The fine spatial resolution enables detailed identification of air pollution hotspots, including locations that are not covered by regulatory monitoring networks

In all pilots, different combinations of components for data ingestion, data harmonization, data enrichment, data modelling and prediction, data storage, data access and data visualization were used including the necessary exposure of the resulting data with the Eclipse Data Connector demonstrating the Dataspace modular concept.

Despite the focus of the project on metadata, only dataset and data service metadata was produced (including data quality indicators, lineage and semantics) as discussed in D4.3. The project missed an opportunity to build service metadata for models and processing workflows.

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ANNEX I: PILOT 1 WATER QUALITY

ANNEX I.1 CROWDWATER INDICATOR SCORING SYSTEM

This section describes the scoring system for the four indicators—nutrients, biotope, lake usage, and waterstress—which are collected based on CrowdWater observations for standing water type. The relevant categories are listed in each table. Seasonal variables are indicated in blue. Unless otherwise specified, indicators are set to “NA” for observation if one of the questions included has not been answered.

CrowdWater Indicator Nutrients

1. Sum of scores per observation
2. Average of all observations per spot

Table 6: Table of nutrient indicator reports.

Positive scores		Negative scores	
Would go swimming	+ 1	Visibility depth 20 – 50 cm	-1
Visibility depth > 1m	+ 1	Visibility depth a few cm	-2
Underwater plants*	+ 1	Duckweed 1/4	-0.25
Water color: clear, blue	+ 1	Duckweed 1/2	-0.5
		Duckweed 3/4	-1
		Complete duckweed cover	-2
		Water color: green, brown	-1
		Smell: Rotten eggs	-1
		Sewage odor	-2

* Question for underwater plants is not obligatory to calculate the indicator

Best possible score: + 4 (Clear water with a high visibility depth and underwater plants)

Neutral score: 0

Worst possible score: -7 (Foul-smelling water, completely covered with duckweed and very low visibility depth)

CrowdWater Indicator Biotope

1. Sum of scores per observation
2. Average of all observations per spot

Table 7: Table of biotope indicator reports.

Positive scores		Negative scores	
Natural lake shore	+ 1	Built-in lake shore	-1
Blue shore vegetation: Reed	+ 1	Lake shore vegetation: Lawn	- 0.5
Lake shore vegetation: Trees	+ 0.5	No lake shore vegetation*	-1
Lake shore vegetation: Other	+ 0.5		
A lot deadwood in the water	+ 1		
Some deadwood in the water	+ 0.5		

Animals: Dragonflies	+1	
Animals: Amphibians	+1	
Animals: Fish	+0.5	
Animals: Waterfowl	+0.5	
Floating leaf plants	+1	
Underwater plants	+1	

* This is assumed if no vegetation is specified and the lake is also specified as completely built-in. If the shore is not specified as completely built-in, it is assumed that the obligatory vegetation input has been omitted.

Best possible score: + 9 (All surveyed organisms present (lake shore vegetation, animals, aquatic plants) with additional natural shoreline and abundant deadwood)

Neutral score: +2 (Some plants in the water or on the shore and water birds visible)

Worst possible score: -2 (Lake completely built-in, without vegetation, no animals or plants visible)

CrowdWater Indicator Lake Usage

1. Sum of scores per observation
2. Average of all observations per spot

Table 8: Table of lake usage scores.

Positive scores		Negative scores	
Usage: Bathing	+ 2		
Usage: Dog bathing	+ 1		
Usage: Fishing	+ 1		
Usage: Water sports	+ 1		
Activities on the shore	+ 0.5		
Lake is accessible	+ 2	No visible usage *	-1

*Only counts if the shore is accessible, so accessibility score is reduced to +1

Best possible score: + 7.5 (Lake is accessible and all uses present)

Neutral score: +2.5 (Lake is accessible and some activities on the shore)

Worst possible score: 0 (Lake is not accessible and no visible usage)

CrowdWater Indicator Water stress

1. One score from the matrix per observation
2. Sum of all observations per spot (--> the more citizens indicate a high water stress the more critical is the situation)

Table 9: Table of water level changes reported in lakes.

		Water level changes			
		High changes	Low changes	No	Unknown
Lake	Yes*	-3	-3	NA	-3

sometimes dries out	No**	-1	-0.5	2	1
	Unknown***	-1.5	-1	2	NA

* Once it is stated that the lake sometimes dries up, the fluctuations are irrelevant for the assessment. A simultaneous assessment of “sometimes dries up” and “no fluctuations” does not make sense and is therefore rated as NA.

** If it is stated that the lake does not dry out, the extent of the fluctuation is decisive. No fluctuation results in positive scores.

*** The same applies here as for the answer “No” in the case of drying up, except that fluctuations are assessed slightly more negatively, as it is not clear whether this could cause the lake to dry.

ANNEX I.2 LIST OF HIGH NUTRIENT CONCENTRATION LAKES

Table 10: Table of lakes of which had at least one high nutrient measurement.

Lake Name	Lake ID	At least one PO ₄ measurement ≥ 0.5 mg/L	At least one NO ₂ measurement ≥ 0.05 mg/L
Barther Pfuhl	582944283	x	
Berl	582944277	x	
Breitkopfbecken	58298481211		x
Britzer Kirchteich	5832331		x
Bucher Schlosspark	58294163	x	
Dillgesteich	58325434	x	x
Dorfteich Bohnsdorf	5832123	x	
Dorfteich Wartenberg	582944267	x	
Elsenteich	58292825		x
Fennpfuhl	582934253		x
Fennsee	5831922121216421		x
Flughafensee, Vorbecken	581967215		x
Freseteich	58325835		x
Friedhofsweiher	5829342123	x	
Grenzteich	582921	x	
Große Moorlinse	582942823	x	
Grundwasserteich	5829533	x	
Grüner Teich	58299511	x	x
Hönowe Weiherkette Bogensee	5829223	x	
Hundekehlesee	583192212121621		x
Karower Teich	582943161	x	
Kiezteich im Ernst- Thälmann-Park	lat: 52.5391, lon: 13.435	x	
Klareensee	58325413	x	
Kleine Moorlinse	lat: 52.6332, lon: 13.4764	x	

Kleiner Teich	58325434121	x	x
Krummer Pfuhl	5832547	x	
Lankegrabenteich	583257223	x	
Lauenburgteich	58325793	x	x
Lietzensee	5829781		x
Nikolassee	58319241	x	
Promenadenteich	5832731	x	
Pücklerteich	583192212121721		x
Schäfersee	58298481		x
Septimerbecken	58298483		x
Spektelake	5878215	x	x
Springpfuhl	58293423	x	x
Stangenpfuhl	583273325	x	
Steinbergsee	5819692893	x	x
Teich Blumeninsel (Tiergartengewässer)	lat: 52.5111, lon: 13.3649		x
Teich Spreeweg (Tiergartengewässer)	lat: 52.5151, lon: 13.3529		x
Waldsee Hermsdorf	58196278125		x
Waldsee Zehlendorf	5831922113		x
Weidenpfuhl	58292231	x	
Weiher Waldowpark	58292823	x	
Ziegeleibecken	581962769	x	x